

POLITECNICO DI MILANO

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Master Degree in Nuclear Engineering

**Ultra-high vacuum characterization of
advanced materials for future particle
accelerators**

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ABSTRACT

This Master thesis has been carried out at the CERN, the European Organization for Nuclear Research. In view of the High Luminosity upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), a new family of materials for the collimation system must be characterized. The collimator materials need to satisfy different requirements in order to intercept particles and protect the superconductive magnets: therefore, a compromise has to be found. So far, the most promising materials are Molybdenum Carbide- Graphite (MoGr) and Copper Diamond (CuCD): these composite materials have good thermo-mechanical and electrical properties, but their compatibility with the Ultra High Vacuum (UHV) of the LHC has to be investigated. A high vacuum level in the LHC is essential to guarantee the beam stability and lifetime; therefore, the outgassing of more than 100 collimators must be taken under control. Two parameters must be verified: the total amount of gas particle outgassed by a collimator and the species of gas. Hydrocarbons, in fact, can affect more the beam and air can saturate the Non Evaporable Getters (NEG), whose pumping speed is of paramount importance to reach UHV.

In order fully characterize the materials, different experimental set-ups were involved: one of the most important parts of the work was performed in vacuum test benches, where the outgassing rate value and the gas analysis of the materials have been evaluated. This analysis was integrated with thermal desorption spectroscopy (TDS): this technic gives a precise indication of all the gases present in the material and the temperature needed to remove them. The surface state of the samples, as well as the internal porosities dimension and connection, are important to determine the outgassing performance of a material. For this reason, different microscopic analysis were also performed. The secondary electron yield (SEY) is likewise important to assess the UHV compatibility of these new

materials in presence of proton beams and it was measured in a dedicated test bench.

From a preliminary study, MoGr was found to be out of the acceptance limits, both in term of outgassing and gas analysis; a huge presence of air was detected. One of the aims of the work has been to understand the source of this huge presence of air: in order to explain the problem, different samples have been vacuum tested and microscopically observed. Besides the characterization of the material as received from the supplier, an important part of the work has been focused on possible thermal and surface treatments able to improve the outgassing performance of the material: they were done to understand if the non-compatibility can be solved with post-production process or if a change in the production process must be foreseen. Moreover, the effects of these treatments give also advice on the steps that have to be taken into account for the final production series.

Conversely, CuCD was found to have a better behaviour, but a compatible cleaning has to be investigated.

SOMMARIO ESTESO

In tutti gli acceleratori di particelle, condizioni di ultra alto vuoto (UHV) sono necessarie per un corretto funzionamento. Lo scattering del fascio accelerato contro i gas residui ne può, infatti, diminuire l'intensità, abbassando quindi la probabilità di collisione delle particelle accelerate nelle zone di misura. La traiettoria delle particelle è determinata dai magneti superconduttori, la cui integrità deve quindi essere garantita. Il contenuto energetico delle particelle è alto, quindi, anche una piccola parte della loro energia, se depositata in un magnete, può determinarne un significativo aumento di temperatura. Qualora essa superasse la *temperatura critica*, il magnete svilupperebbe una resistenza elettrica, diventando un normale conduttore. Questo fenomeno è noto come *quench* del magnete. Pertanto, negli acceleratori di particelle, è necessario un sistema che prevenga la collisione delle particelle fuori traiettoria con i superconduttori. Questa funzione è svolta dai collimatori che, grazie alla loro vicinanza al fascio, ne intercettano le particelle più esterne. Inoltre, in caso di un errore di orbita dell'intero fascio, essi dovranno fermarlo per evitare il suo impatto contro parti più delicate della macchina. Un collimatore è formato principalmente da una camera a vuoto in acciaio inossidabile, all'interno della quale sono disposti due blocchi di collimazione paralleli, detti mascelle. Ogni blocco di collimazione è costituito da una trave di Glidcop, una lega di rame, brasata a dei circuiti di raffreddamento in rame-nichel. I tubi, a sezione esterna quadrata, vengono brasati anche ad un'altra piastra di Glidcop, progettata per contenere dei blocchi di materiale assorbitore, che interfacciano le particelle fuori dalla traiettoria nominale. I materiali assorbitori dovranno quindi possedere eccellenti caratteristiche: proprietà termiche per resistere all'aumento di temperatura indotto dalla deposizione di energia del fascio, proprietà di resistenza alla radiazione e, qualora il fascio sia composto da particelle cariche, essi dovranno anche avere una elevata conducibilità elettrica. In presenza di particelle cariche in moto, infatti, nei

materiali circostanti viene indotta una corrente che a sua volta può perturbare il fascio; deve pertanto essere limitata. La loro densità deve essere alta abbastanza per garantire l'assorbimento di un numero rilevante di particelle, ma non troppo elevata poiché la deposizione di energia del fascio li distruggerebbe. Inoltre, per poter operare in un ambiente di UHV, il loro degassaggio deve essere compatibile con i valori di pressione che si vogliono mantenere nel sistema. Nessuno dei materiali esistenti può soddisfare al meglio tutte queste esigenze, pertanto un compromesso deve essere trovato. Nel Large Hadron Collider (LHC), l'acceleratore di particelle più esteso al mondo e situato al CERN, il sistema di collimazione ideato per adempiere queste funzioni è un sistema multi-fase a densità crescente. I collimatori primari sono i più vicini al fascio, pertanto hanno una densità non troppo alta perché verrebbero distrutti. A valle di essi, ancora un elevato numero di particelle non è stato intercettato: per questo sono installati collimatori secondari e terziari a densità maggiore, ma più lontani dal fascio. Ad oggi, il compromesso migliore è stato individuato nella grafite rinforzata con fibre di carbonio (CFC), per i collimatori primari e secondari, e in una lega di tungsteno per i terziari. In vista dell'up-grade di LHC (High Luminosity, HL-LHC), mirato ad aumentare la probabilità di collisione, nuovi materiali per la collimazione sono stati studiati: il principale obiettivo è quello di diminuire il loro contributo all'impedenza dell'acceleratore. Fino ad ora i materiali più interessanti sono due compositi: il molibdeno-grafite (MoGr) e il rame-diamante (CuCD). Lo scopo di questo lavoro di tesi è stato quello di caratterizzare il loro comportamento in un ambiente UHV come quello di un acceleratore, i cui requisiti sono molto spinti. Per una caratterizzazione completa dei materiali, differenti apparati sperimentali sono stati utilizzati. Un'ampia parte del lavoro si è focalizzato sulla determinazione del degassaggio dei materiali, ovvero del numero di molecole di gas uscenti dal materiale per unità di tempo. In ogni acceleratore, infatti, la capacità di pompaggio è una quantità fissata; pertanto, per mantenere una bassa pressione il degassaggio va limitato. Queste misure sono state effettuate in dei banchi prova forniti di pompe capaci di portare a livelli di UHV e sistemi di

monitoraggio della pressione. Tuttavia, è noto che la probabilità di scattering delle particelle del fascio è maggiore per alcuni gas, soprattutto quelli più pesanti. Pertanto non basta garantire un buon livello di vuoto, ma anche le specie emesse dai materiali vanno monitorate: i componenti inseriti in LHC devono essere privi di contaminanti e in particolare di idrocarburi pesanti a bassa tensione di vapore, che verrebbero quindi emessi all'interfaccia con un basso livello di pressione. Ogni misura di degasaggio è stata pertanto accompagnata da un'analisi dei gas. A complemento, sono state svolte anche analisi di spettroscopia di desorbimento termico (TDS): con questa tecnica, i gas emessi dal materiale in esame vengono costantemente monitorati durante il suo riscaldamento. Il degasaggio di un materiale dipende dalla sua composizione chimica, ma anche dalla sua configurazione microscopica. Le porosità dei materiali possono, infatti, intrappolare i gas e successivamente rilasciarli quando il materiale si trova in un ambiente di UHV. Per questo, diversi provini, dopo essere testati nei banchi prova di degasaggio, sono stati osservati con tecniche microscopiche avanzate. Attraverso questa caratterizzazione, si è voluto indagare sulla qualità del materiale così come esso si trova alla fine del processo di produzione. La parte successiva del lavoro si è poi focalizzata sulla valutazione dell'effetto di trattamenti termici e superficiali. Alcuni di essi, sono considerati obbligatori prima dell'installazione nell'acceleratore. Un trattamento termico ad alta temperatura e sotto vuoto (detto *vacuum firing*) è sempre applicato prima dell'installazione sia alle camere a vuoto in acciaio inox, sia ai materiali per la collimazione per diminuire il degasaggio. Inoltre, per diminuire ulteriormente l'impedenza dei collimatori, è stata presa in considerazione l'opzione di applicare un coating metallico sugli assorbitori. L'impatto sul degasaggio di alcuni trattamenti necessari per la preparazione superficiale prima del coating è stato analizzato. La maggior parte del lavoro si è incentrata sul MoGr, poichè si sono trovati problemi di degasaggio di aria: alcune delle molecole presenti nell'aria, soprattutto l'azoto, saturano la capacità di pompaggio del coating di materiale getter non evaporabile (NEG) applicato sulle pareti della camera a vuoto e il cui pompaggio contribuisce in modo fondamentale

al raggiungimento di un livello di UHV in LHC. Capire la sorgente di questa eccessiva presenza di aria è stato uno degli obiettivi di questo lavoro. Di questo materiale, è stata valutata anche la resa di emissione di elettroni secondari (SEY), altro criterio fondamentale per stabilire la compatibilità di un materiale con un acceleratore di particelle cariche. La caratterizzazione del CuCD, seppure meno estesa, è stata molto importante per stabilire quali devono essere i successivi step per comprendere il degasaggio del materiale.

Nel *Capitolo 1*, la tesi viene contestualizzata: per prima cosa viene introdotto il CERN, il centro di ricerca in cui si è svolto per 12 mesi questo lavoro. Tra i diversi acceleratori presenti nella struttura, una parte di rilievo è stata data al Large Hadron Collider (LHC) e alle avanzate tecnologie che ne permettono il funzionamento. Tra di esse, il sistema di collimazione e quello di vuoto sono descritti in dettaglio, vista la loro rilevanza per il presente lavoro: ne è descritta la struttura e le principali caratteristiche. In particolare, per quanto riguarda i collimatori, sono state approfondite le proprietà che devono avere gli assorbitori, la parte del collimatore che più interagisce con il fascio. Questa sezione è molto importante per capire i principi che portano ad individuare i possibili materiali per nuovi acceleratori. Infine, le motivazioni e i requisiti che serviranno per l'upgrade HL-LHC sono presentati.

Nel *Capitolo 2*, come prima cosa, viene spiegata la filosofia seguita per la selezione dei due materiali presenti in questo lavoro: il MoGr e il CuCD. Si descrivono, poi, le principali caratteristiche termo-meccaniche ed elettriche dei due materiali compositi. Inoltre, i processi produttivi vengono descritti: questa parte è importante perché i materiali per applicazioni di UHV richiedono accortezze talvolta molto maggiori a quelle richieste da impieghi standard. Le atmosfere di compattazione e sinterizzazione di questi materiali, così come la successiva manipolazione, possono influire sul loro degasaggio ed è quindi importante conoscerli.

Il *Capitolo 3*, si può dividere in due parti: nella prima vengono introdotte alcune definizioni utilizzate nelle tecnologie UHV e si descrivono i principali processi che possono avvenire in un sistema a vuoto (*degassing*, *desorption*, *outgassing*) e le unità di misura coinvolte. Inoltre, una parte è dedicata ai metodi noti per diminuire il degasaggio di un materiale: gli effetti del *bake-out* e del *vacuum firing* vengono esposti con particolare riferimento agli acciai inossidabili, il cui comportamento in vuoto è stato dettagliatamente studiato. Nella seconda parte invece, si spiegano i criteri di accettazione che determinano la compatibilità o meno di un materiale con l'ambiente UHV di LHC. Questa parte è fondamentale per capire il criterio usato per valutare i risultati delle misure effettuate.

Nel *Capitolo 4* si descrivono tutti i set-up sperimentali utilizzati per la caratterizzazione dei materiali e i principi di funzionamento delle diverse strumentazioni. Inoltre, il metodo di calcolo del degasaggio e la procedura utilizzata per i test vengono presentati.

Il *Capitolo 5* è dedicato alla presentazione dei risultati sperimentali: la prima parte riguarda lo studio del MoGr, la seconda quella del CuCD. L'analisi dei gas e il valore di degasaggio di diversi provini viene confrontato per individuare analogie e differenze di comportamento. Per il MoGr, si è utilizzato come riferimento la grafite utilizzata in altri collimatori: degasaggi, TDS e immagini microscopiche dei due materiali sono state confrontate. Numerosi trattamenti termici e superficiali sono stati applicati e il risultato dei test analizzato per una migliore comprensione del problema. L'analisi del CuCD, seppur ad una fase iniziale, fornisce spunti per ulteriori approfondimenti.

Infine, nel *Capitolo 6*, vengono presentate le conclusioni, frutto dell'analisi di tutte le misure eseguite. Inoltre, vengono esposti quali dovranno essere gli ulteriori test che dovranno completare il presente lavoro.

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CHAPTER 1

The Large Hadron Collider

1.1 Introduction

After the Second World War, the idea of a European atomic laboratory started growing up from a handful of visionary scientists: the aim of the project was to unite European scientists to restore their distinction and to share the huge costs of nuclear physics facilities. An important contribution to this project was given by Louis de Broglie: the scientist carried out the first official proposal for the creation of a European laboratory at the European Cultural Conference, which opened in Lausanne in 1949. At the fifth UNESCO General Conference, the Nobel laureate Isidor Rabi underlined the necessity of creating regional research laboratories to enhance international scientific collaboration. Their ambition came true in 1952, when 11 countries signed an agreement establishing the provisional European Council for Nuclear Research (*Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire*), under the acronym of CERN and few months later Geneva was selected as a building site. In 1954, at the sixth session of the council, the convention establishing the organisation was signed and then ratified by the 12 founding Member States: Belgium, Denmark, France, the Federal Republic of Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, and Yugoslavia. Nowadays 22 member states and 5 associate members are part of CERN; a lot of others countries have cooperation agreements.

Figure 1: Third section of the provisional CERN council in Amsterdam on the 4th October 1952. At this section, Geneva was chosen as the site for the future laboratories.

The incredible successes obtained in the following years proved the benefit of this cooperation. Among them, the first observation of antinuclei (antideuteron) in 1965 should be mentioned, since it opened the way to antimatter study, an important field of modern physics, as well as the invention World Wide Web by Tim Berners-Lee in 1989, one of the discoveries with the higher social impact of the history. [1]

The first CERN accelerator was built in 1957: the 600 MeV Synchrocyclotron provided beams for particle and nuclear physics. During years, different accelerators were realised: advanced technology has been used and developed to obtain beams with increasing energy, in order to investigate sub-nuclear particle structure. Nowadays, one of the main roles of this set of accelerators is to feed the beam pipes of the world's largest and most powerful particle accelerator: the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), a two-ring, superconducting collider with a circumference of 27 km.

Figure 2: The CERN accelerator complex

The proton chain starts from a bottle of hydrogen gas: the only electron of the atom is stripped off through an electric field. The first accelerator is a linear machine named LINAC 2, able to inject 50 MeV protons in the Proton Synchrotron Booster (PSB). At the exit of the PSB protons of 1.4 GeV move forward to the Proton Synchrotron (PS) which pushes the beam up to 25 GeV. Before entering in the LHC, the protons are further accelerated to 450 GeV by the Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS). In the LHC the protons are separated into two beams, circulating in opposite directions and in parallel pipes up to a maximum energy of 7 TeV. It should be noticed that the beams are not continuous, but they are divided in *bunches*. During operation, a maximum number of 2808 bunches could be injected in the LHC; each bunch is composed by $1.15 \cdot 10^{11}$ particles.

Also, lead ions can be accelerated in the LHC: they are extracted from vaporised lead, injected in the LINAC 3 and successively brought to the Low

Energy Ion Ring (LEIR). After that, they follow the same route of protons.

Once the beams have reached their maximum energy, they are ready to collide inside four detectors, where the total energy at the collision point is 14 TeV in the centre-of-mass: A Large Hadron Collider Experiment (ALICE), A Toroidal LHC ApparatuS (ATLAS), Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) and Large Hadron Collider Beauty (LHCb). [2]

One of the most important parameters, to evaluate the performance of the accelerator complex, is the number of events per second generated in LHC collisions:

$$N_{event} = L \cdot \sigma_{event}$$

Where:

- σ_{event} is the cross section for the event under study [barns]
- L is a probability of collision, called luminosity [$\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]

The total cross section of proton-proton interaction increases with the energy of the particles and the machine luminosity depends on different beam parameters. A peak luminosity of $10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ is expected in the two high-luminosity experiments, ATLAS and CMS.

In order to achieve this luminosity, an advanced technology is required: radio-frequency cavities accelerate the particles and superconductive magnets¹ are required to bend and focus the beam. The cables of the magnets are made of Nb-Ti, kept at a temperature below 2 K with superfluid helium to maximise the field

¹ Superconductive material are characterized by having zero resistance under a certain temperature (critical temperature). Therefore current dissipation is minimized and with the same amount of power injected, the resulting magnetic field can be much higher.

strength. A cryogenic system is thus essential in the LHC ring [3]. For a proper operation of LHC, a well-structured vacuum environment and collimation system are required. Their main function and figures will be explained in details in the next paragraphs.

1.2 Beam cleaning and collimation system

The superconductive magnets, guiding the particle beams in the LHC pipes, can lose their superconductivity: the phenomenon is known as *quench*. When the coil overcomes the critical temperature, the electric conductor which forms the magnet develops a finite resistance, therefore the energy stored in the magnetic field is converted into heat by Joule effect. The dissipated power heats and induces quenches also in other parts of the magnet, which rapidly becomes a normal conductor [4]. The huge amount of particle travelling in LHC leads to a stored energy up to 362 MJ, a billion times larger than the typical magnet quench limits. For this reason, high power accelerators cannot operate without a system able to reduce the unavoidable losses due to beam-beam or beam-gas interactions. Therefore a high energy particle accelerator needs the presence of collimators to clean the beam and protect the machine. The first function must be fulfilled by collimation system during the nominal operation: the beam cleaning is realised through the interception of the beam halo, consisting of particles deviating from the ideal trajectory, to limit the thermal losses and hence the quench probability in magnets. Moreover, collimators should also prevent, in the case of beam orbit error, the beam impact against delicate machine devices. A collimator must be able to survive to the impact of one or more proton bunches, withstanding a huge amount of energy deposition in a very short time.

To fulfil its functions, the best layout of the collimation system is a multi-stage cleaning process (see Figure 3). Primary collimators are the closest to the beam and intercept lost protons: part of the beam is absorbed, but there is also a

shower of generated particles that leave the collimator with a different energy leading to the secondary beam halo. For this reason also secondary collimators are needed, but also tertiary to intercept tertiary halo coming from the secondary leaks.

Figure 3: Scheme of the LHC collimation system, courtesy of E. Quaranta.

The collimators are placed in a position such that secondary halo impact against superconductive magnet is avoided. For machine protection and halo cleaning, it would be better to have collimators very close to the beam, but some limitations must be taken into account: the distance must be enough to avoid excessive impedance to the beam, which can lead to beam instabilities, and to limit thermo-mechanical loads on collimators. The heating and the deformation of too close collimator would be much higher.

In order to constrain the beam halo in all the directions, each collimator is made by two jaws enclosed in a stainless steel vacuum tank (see Figure 4 and 5); several collimators are installed, with different orientation: in LHC we can find horizontal, vertical or oblique collimators [5].

Figure 4: A LHC collimator with the vacuum tank open, left, and a "beam's eye-view" of the collimator aperture, right, courtesy of S. Redaelli.

Inside each jaw, different absorber materials intercept beam particles and absorb most of the thermal loads.

Figure 5: 3D view of LHC collimator. The absorber blocks, inside the jaw, see directly the beam.

1.2.1 Current collimation materials

The collimator absorber must have different properties to fulfil properly the beam cleaning and the machine protection [6]:

- High electrical conductivity to limit wall impedance²
- High thermal conductivity to bear steady-state losses without losing geometrical stability
- Low coefficient of thermal expansion, high specific heat and ultimate strength to improve thermal shock resistance in case of beam orbit error
- High melting and degradation temperature to withstand the high temperature reached in case of accident
- A very low radiation-induced degradation to increase component lifetime
- Low outgassing rate to be compatible with the Ultra High Vacuum (UHV) environment of LHC
- Low secondary electron yield to limit electron cloud formation (more details will be given in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5)
- A well-balanced density to limit peak energy deposition, while maintaining sufficient cleaning efficiency. This property depends on the category of collimators: the absorber material of primary and secondary collimators should have a low density to limit the energy deposition of the particles, since the jaws are very close to the beam and they must withstand accidental impact without significant damage. Tertiary collimators are less exposed to the beam, so their density can be increased to absorb particle in a more effective way: their cleaning efficiency is very

² Each proton is a charged particle in motion, which induces currents and fields in the surrounding materials. In turns, these fields perturb all the other protons; in order to minimize the perturbation, the wall impedance must be as small as possible.

important to protect the magnets and to clean the beam before and after the experiments.

The material choice must realize a compromise between all these needs: at the moment, carbon fibre-reinforced graphite (CFC) and a tungsten alloy achieve the best compromise. The CFC is the absorber in the current installed primary and secondary collimators: this composite material is made of a graphite matrix filled with carbon fibre, which reinforces the material thanks to their high strength and increases both thermal and electrical conductivity [7]. The graphite has good thermal properties and, thanks to its low density, the energy deposition and hence the radiation damage are minimised. The main disadvantage of carbon-carbon composites is the poor electrical conductivity that leads to high induced RF impedance. On the other hand, a tungsten alloy is chosen for tertiary collimators, but its robustness to beam impact is quite poor [8].

The collimator jaws, in which the absorbers are contained, should also minimise the RF impedance contribution and the thermal-induced deformation to ensure good geometrical stability [9]: these requirements are satisfied by Glidcop, a special alloy with copper-based metal matrix mixed with aluminum oxide particles, to increase strength at high temperature and radiation hardness [10].

1.3 Vacuum system

Nuclear scattering of protons against residual gas is one of the main source of heat to the 1.9 K helium circuit and also a limitation to beam intensity, hence an appropriate vacuum level should guarantee adequate beam lifetime as well as a low background to the experiments. The nuclear cross section for beam-gas interactions strongly depends on the gas, as it is shown in Table 1 [3].

Table 1: The nuclear scattering cross sections at 7 TeV for different gases and the corresponding densities and equivalent pressure for a 100 h lifetime

GAS	Nuclear scattering cross section [cm²]	Gas density [m⁻³] for a 100 h lifetime	Pressure [mbar] at 5 K for a 100 h lifetime
H₂	$9.5 \cdot 10^{-26}$	$9.8 \cdot 10^{14}$	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$
He	$1.26 \cdot 10^{-25}$	$7.4 \cdot 10^{14}$	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
CH₄	$5.66 \cdot 10^{-25}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{14}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
H₂O	$5.65 \cdot 10^{-25}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{14}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
CO	$8.54 \cdot 10^{-25}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{14}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$
CO₂	$1.32 \cdot 10^{-24}$	$7 \cdot 10^{13}$	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-9}$

In LHC three different vacuum system can be found: 48 km of insulation vacuum for helium distribution lines to avoid heat load by gas conduction, 42 km of Ultra High Vacuum (UHV) at cryogenic temperature for cryomagnets and 6 km of UHV beam pipes at room temperature, in areas called Long Straight Sections (LSS) [11].

1.3.1 The long straight sections

The room temperature sectors have the most stringent requirements for the vacuum level: they serve as experimental or utility insertion and thus to minimise experiment background and beam luminosity losses, the pressure should range between 10^{-10} and 10^{-11} mbar. In the LHC ring, eight different LSS can be individuated (see Figure 6): four of these are dedicated to the experiments (LSS1 and LSS5 to the high luminosity experiments ATLAS and CMS, LSS2 and LSS8

to ALICE and LHCb, the low luminosity ones). LSS3 and LSS7 are dedicated to collimation, LSS4 to the radio-frequency cavities for proton acceleration and LSS6 to beam ejection system.

Figure 6: Schematic view of the LHC with the location of the 8 LSS.

The LSS pipes are made of low-oxygen content silver-softened copper or stainless steel and they are coated with TiZrV non-evaporable getters (NEG): the pumping contribution of NEG is mandatory to reach an acceptable value of pressure also in the insertion points; their main figures and requirements will be explained in Appendix A. Their maximum length is almost 7 m, compatible with the existing chemical cleaning baths at CERN. These pipes are connected by stainless steel bellows with radio-frequency copper screen to reduce the longitudinal impedance seen by the beam: half of them are fitted with diagnostic port and pumping ports that house all metal valves needed to start the pump-down.

Moreover, sector valves separate cryogenic and room temperature sectors: they are fitted with ion pump and a set of gauges to monitor the pressure, together

with a residual gas analyser to check the composition of the gases present in the system (see Figure 7) [11].

Figure 7: Schematic view of one typical sector of the LHC's Long Straight Sections.

LSS3 and LSS7 comprise 9 and 19 movable collimators per beam, respectively. Each collimator with its vacuum tank is surrounded on both side by ion pump with NEG cartridges to increase the pumping speed, since a boost of pressure is expected for different reasons in correspondence of the beam cleaning devices. First, the absorber materials have an outgassing rate higher than the stainless steel or the copper used for the pipes; secondly, due to the vicinity to the beam, collimator absorber are affected by stimulated desorption of gases induced by radiation and radiation effects (thermal desorption, photon and electron desorption,..).

The aim in these regions is to obtain and maintain a static pressure of $5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mbar: the pumping speed cannot be arbitrarily increased due to limited space, therefore the outgassing of the collimator has to be minimised. A detailed explanation of the limit value of outgassing rate will be given in Chapter 3.

1.4 High luminosity upgrade requirements

The number of collisions is a fundamental parameter to increase the physics time: the higher the experimental data available, the higher the possibility to detect rare processes and new particles. The number of events can be increased either with a bigger cross section (e.g. higher beam energy) or enhancing the probability of collision, the luminosity. The high luminosity project of LHC (HL-LHC), approved in 2014, aims at obtaining a bigger number of collisions through a higher luminosity (a factor 5 beyond its design value) and it should be operational by 2025. The achievement of the HL-LHC goals is based on different technological innovations, covering different engineering fields. Among them, new superconductive magnets and new superconductive radio frequency cavities should be noticed [12].

The higher luminosity will involve higher beam current and higher thermal loads which must be sustained by all the machine devices, in particular by the collimation system. The beam stored energy will surpass 700 MJ, thus even a loss of a tiny fraction of the beam will cause a magnet quench; for this reason, the collimator cleaning efficiency must be improved. The higher losses level also impose severe conditions on the collimators themselves: their robustness against losses must be guaranteed for an adequate lifetime, both for normal and accidental cases. The carbon-fibre-carbon composites (CFC) are designed to withstand the impact with all the injected beam without significant permanent damage, but their high impedance, related to the poor CFC electrical conductivity, leads to beam instability at high intensities. For this reason, a new collimator material R&D programmed has been launched, aiming at finding low impedance materials able to withstand the HL losses: a good compromise between electrical and thermo-mechanical properties should be reached. Simultaneously, a new advanced design of the collimator jaw is being studied. [8]

CHAPTER 2

Collimator materials for HL-LHC

The strategy, applied to fulfil the increased collimator challenges required by HL-LHC, has been based on the combination of graphite or diamond, which thanks to their low density, high thermal conductivity and low thermal expansion bear high thermal load, with metal or transition metal based ceramics, possessing high mechanical strength and good electrical conductivity. So far, the best candidates identified are molybdenum carbide- graphite (MoGr) and copper-diamond (CuCD). [8]

2.1 Molybdenum carbide-graphite

The development of this novel material has been carried out in a collaboration between CERN and an Italian enterprise, BrevettiBizz.

Molybdenum is chosen for the good thermal properties (high melting point, low coefficient of thermal expansion) as well as very high mechanical strength and electrical conductivity. Graphite features low density and excellent service temperature. Moreover, if a good graphitization is reached, excellent thermal conductivity and low coefficient of thermal expansion are obtained. These characteristics, together with the low average atomic number of the material ($Z \sim 6.5$ due to the smallness of the Mo fraction), make this ceramic-matrix composite the ideal successor of CFC for primary and secondary collimators.

During 5 years, 15 different grades have been produced and thermo-mechanically tested; the two investigated in this work will be presented.

2.1.1 Production process

The production of this novel composite material starts from molybdenum and graphite powders, which are mixed together in a dry mixer machine. The two grades involved use graphite powder grade 3260 from Asbury Carbons Company: the spheroidal-flake morphology enhances the compaction process and limits the anisotropy of the final material (see Figure 8). A small amount of titanium is found to increase the electrical conductivity.

Figure 8: The microstructure of the Asbury 3260 spheroidal-flake graphite powders.

Different compositions have been devised during years, but the two grades examined here present the same initial powder composition, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Initial powders composition for the two grades of interest

Initial volume % Mo	4.5
Initial volume % Gr	95.3
Initial volume % Ti	0.2

It was decided to name the different grades indicating by an appropriate codes their initial volumetric composition, as it is shown in Figure 9 and Table 3.

Figure 9: Convention used to name the different grades of MoGr.

Table 3: Two examples of MoGr grades and their compositions

Grade name	% vol Mo	% vol Gr	% vol C fibres	% vol Ti
MG6403	4.5	95.3	0	0.2
MG6541	4.5	90.9	4.76 (short fibres)	0.048

The two grades studied in this work are thus both called MG6403, but some differences are present in the production processes, as it is explained below.

After the powder mixture preparation, in fact, the production process can be divided into three steps:

- Uniaxial compaction of the so-called green body: the powders, inside a steel die, are compressed in a hydraulic press at 300MPa. The graphite crystallites are oriented with the basal plane perpendicular to the pressing direction³.

The older grade (called MG6403Fc) is compressed at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. The green compaction of the new one (MG6403He) was conceived in order to minimise the exposure to air of the powders when they are not well compacted and, therefore, to reduce trapped air in the final compacted body. A primary vacuum ($10^{-1} \div 10^{-3}$ mbar) is reached in the chamber with open mould, then the temperature is increased up to 250° C to enhance the thermal degassing of the powders. At this point, the mould is closed and the compaction started. Before opening the chamber, argon is injected to vent the system to atmospheric pressure.

- Spark plasma sintering (SPS) is a technique characterised by heating of the powders by Joule effect, produced by an electrical current; hence the heating rate is quite fast. The best results in term of thermomechanical and electrical properties were obtained with a temperature of 2600°C and a duration of almost 1200 seconds.

During this phase, molybdenum reacts with carbon forming stable carbide. The sintering temperature is above the melting point of these carbides, which become liquid during sintering: for this reason, the process is also called liquid-phase sintering. It is found that the liquid phase enhances the graphitization of the material as well as applying pressure during sintering: thus, the green body is put into a tailor made graphite

³ The orientation is possible also during the cold compaction because the sliding of the planes is enhanced by the high anisotropy of the graphite grains.

mould (Figure 10) with top and bottom punches and a lateral container in which is heated while applying a pressure of 35MPa.

The atmosphere during sintering is a primary vacuum for both MG6403Fc and MG6403He: for the first grade, the gas used to vent is air while for the second is argon.

Figure 10: Schematic of the sintering machined used. Courtesy of J. Guardia.

- Post-sintering, pressure-less heat treatment in order to release the internal stress from the previous cycle. The maximum temperature is almost 2600°C and the duration 3000 seconds. Sintering and post-sintering are done in the same machine, but the mould configuration is different (Figure 11). The atmosphere and venting gas are the same as for sintering.

Figure 11: Pressure-less post-sintering treatment.

A summary of the process characteristic for the two grades is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Production process parameters for MG6403Fc and MG64-3He

	MG6403Fc	MG6403He
Powder compaction	P=300 MPa T= room T Atmosphere: air	P=300 MPa T= 250°C Atmosphere: vacuum
Sintering	T=2600°C Duration= 2400 s Atmosphere: vacuum Venting gas: air	T=2600°C Duration= 2400 s Atmosphere: vacuum Venting gas: argon
Post sintering	T=2600°C Duration= 2400 s Atmosphere: vacuum Venting gas: air	T=2600°C Duration= 2400 s Atmosphere: vacuum Venting gas: argon

Different machines and different mould configuration are used for the aforementioned production stages, hence between each production step the plate is exposed to air.

At the end of the process, a plate of 100x150 mm with a thickness of 30 mm is ready to be cut and machined to obtain specimen for the characterization and collimator blocks for prototypes (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: MoGr plate after post-sintering process.

Due to the stringent tolerance limit, an accurate machining of the material is an essential step of the production process. The presence of hard molybdenum carbides does not influence the machinability of the samples, which can be treated with the same tools used for other graphitic materials. The machine used to fabricate blocks for a full-size collimator test (Figure 13) is a Computer Numerical Control apparatus (CNC). Moreover, to ensure UHV compatibility, lubricants must be avoided and an aspiration with filter is mandatory to remove the surface powders [13].

Figure 13: Machined blocks for full-size collimator component.

2.1.2 Thermo-mechanical and electrical properties

During the sintering, part of the liquid phase leaks out: for this reason, it is difficult to evaluate the final theoretical composition and density of the material. The measured final density is around 2.5 g/cm^3 .

Due to the uniaxial compaction, the material is highly oriented and its properties show a transversally orthotropic behaviour: in the in-plane direction, which is indicated as II, the stronger interatomic bond leads to better properties, as can be seen in Table 5. The thermo-mechanical and electrical properties are mainly related to temperature and duration of sintering and post-sintering, so can be considered equal for the two grades.

Table 5: Thermo-mechanical properties of MoGr latest grades

	MG6403Fc/He	
		⊥
Density [$\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$]	2.55	
Electrical conductivity [$\text{MS}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$]	0.95	0.07
Specific heat at 20°C [$\text{J}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$]	0.62	
Thermal diffusivity at 20°C [$\text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	466	31
Thermal conductivity at 20°C [$\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$]	740	50
Coefficient of thermal expansion 20÷200°C	2.7	7.9
Residual deformation [%]	0.00	0.12
Flexural strength [MPa]	58.1±8	10±1
Elastic modulus [GPa]	60.4	4.0

The main figure to be noticed is the in-plane electrical conductivity: it is almost 5 times higher than CFC and 10 times higher than high-quality isotropic graphite.

Because of this characteristic and to the good thermal properties of the graphite matrix, MoGr is a very good candidate for the low impedance primary and secondary collimators [13].

2.1.3 Microstructure observation

Performing a microscopic observation of the material, one can see that the production process leads to a uniform distribution of the carbides on the surface of the material, as we can see in Figure 14. While if we zoom, as in Figure 15, the irregular pattern generated by the graphite planes becomes more evident: some flakes can be not well attached to the surface and sometimes they can also detach.

Figure 14: Surface observation of a MoGr sample.

Figure 15 Microscopic observation of detached grain of a MoGr sample.

Looking at the fracture surface in Figure 16, perpendicular to the basal plane, the preferred elongation of the grains, in the direction perpendicular to the compaction force, can be seen.

Figure 16: Fracture cross section of MoGr sample perpendicular to basal plane.

The techniques used for microscopic observation are detailed in Chapter 4.

2.2 Copper diamond

Copper is an excellent thermal and electrical conductor, but its properties can be further improved with the diamond addition: it reduces the density and the coefficient of thermal expansion, while enhancing the thermal conductivity. The average atomic number of the material is higher than MoGr ($Z \sim 11.4$): therefore, the copper diamond absorbers are suitable for tertiary collimators, where a greater cleaning efficiency is mandatory. Moreover, thanks to its outstanding thermal properties, copper-diamond could be a good solution also for the collimator jaws. Anyway, these thermal figures are very interesting also for industrial application: in fact, CuCD has been applied as a heat sink for electronic devices.

In spite of these advantages, the main problem with this material is the poor chemical affinity between the two elements: a lack of bonding between copper and diamond would worsen the strength and the thermal conductivity. Thus, a third element (*i.e.* boron, chromium, molybdenum, etc.) must be added to enhance the internal bonding of the material through the formation of carbides at the diamond-copper interface. [8]

The grades tested in this work are produced with the adding of boron or chromium.

2.2.1 Production process

At the beginning of the production process, copper, diamond and a carbide-forming material powders are mixed together. The standard initial volumetric composition of the powders is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: CuCD powders composition

Initial volume % D	50-60
Initial volume % Cu	balance
Initial volume % Cr	0-2

The upper limit of the diamond percentage is forced by the requirement of a good compaction, that it is increased also through diamonds of different size in order to achieve a better filling of the interstitial.

The process is similar to the production of MoGr: the powders are pressed at room temperature and then the so-called green is sintered by SPS using a pressure of 35 MPa and a temperature slightly below the melting of copper (around 1000 °C). This process takes 1-4 hours and it is done under dry hydrogen atmosphere. It is then followed by a controlled cooling to 400°C. A successive

stress relieving treatment at 300-400°C can be performed for one hour.⁴ Due to its hardness, the machinability of the CuCD is very challenging: small samples with constant thickness can be cut by water-jet (see Figure 17), but for more complicated shapes and stringent tolerance limits as for the collimator absorber, a copper cladding is applied at the top and the bottom of the sample to facilitate the finishing by conventional machining(see Figure 18).

Figure 17: CuCD plate produced by RHP after water jet cutting.

Figure 18: CuCD blocks produced for LHC collimator prototype with copper.

⁴ Source: RHP technology

2.2.2 Thermo-mechanical and electrical properties

Thanks to the excellent diamond properties, the coefficient of thermal expansion is reduced by a factor 2-3 with respect the pure copper. The thermal and electrical conductivity are good as well. All the properties, relevant for collimation purpose, are summarized in Table 7. The properties refer to a grade containing boron as a binder.

Table 7: Thermo-mechanical properties of CuCD

	CuCD
Density [$\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$]	5.4
Electrical conductivity [$\text{MS}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$]	12.6
Thermal conductivity at 20°C [$\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$]	490
Coefficient of thermal expansion 20÷900°C	6-12
Flexural strength [MPa]	70
Elastic modulus [GPa]	220

The main limitation in the use of this grade is related to the material properties degradation above 250°C: it still not clear if this is related to a thermal degradation of the carbides or to the different thermal expansion coefficient of the copper and the diamond. This aspect is not covered by the scope of this thesis, but it must be taken into account because it excludes the possibility of doing a vacuum firing on the material: such treatment, as explained in Chapter 4, is one of the more employed techniques to reduce the outgassing rate. The problem can be overcome using chromium instead of boron, as this leads to a stronger bond between the matrix and the diamond particle.

CHAPTER 3

Vacuum requirements

Beam losses and beam lifetime are affected by the vacuum level: it is thus important to know the vacuum performance of each materials prior its use in an accelerator.

3.1 Material outgassing

3.1.1 Definitions

In a vacuum system, the gas density and so the pressure level can be affected and limited by external sources (air leaks) but also from the particular materials used in the vacuum chambers or beam vacuum equipment that could be an important source of gas production.

Gas sources in a material are different: if a solid surface, surrounded by gas molecules, is considered, they can bind together by van der Waal's forces (physisorption) or by chemical binding (chemisorption). These molecules may diffuse into the bulk before dissolving: this process is known as absorption [12]. Polymers, thanks to their opened structure, can dissolve important quantity of gases: for this reason, their vacuum behaviour is quite different and it will not be taken into account in this discussion. The porosities (both superficial and in the bulk) of the materials could also be a trap for the gases: the pores can be filled during production process under inert gas atmosphere or when the material is exposed to the atmosphere. Finally, after manufacturing, the surface of the material can be covered by contaminants, typically hydrocarbons that can impact both vacuum level and cleanliness.

Gas molecules are thus present both in the surface and in the bulk of the materials. The removal of these molecules depends upon their location: if the surface gases are considered, they must have enough energy to overcome desorption or binding energy (E_d) to be released. When the dissolved molecules are considered, it has to be taken into account that they need to diffuse toward the surface before being removed: it is, thus, a time-dependent process. Moreover, it should be considered that the gas removal can be either spontaneous or deliberate. Taking into account all these aspects, it is possible to distinguish different phenomena at the solid-gas interphase [12]:

- Degassing is the deliberate removal of gas from a solid or a liquid.
- Desorption is the release of adsorbed chemical species from the surface of a solid.
- Outgassing is the spontaneous evolution of gas from solid or liquid. We can define the measured outgassing rate as the difference between the quantity of gas per unit time leaving the surface and the quantity of reabsorbed gases. If we consider the ideal gas equation of state, we can measure the outgassing rate in $\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, considering constant temperature:

$$P \cdot V = N \cdot k_B \cdot T$$

Where:

- P is the pressure [mbar]
- V is the volume [l]
- N is the number of molecules
- k_B is the Boltzmann constant [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$]
- T is the temperature [K]

A sketch of the three mechanisms is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Schematic of the different process at the solid-gas interface. From the left side: degassing, desorption and outgassing.

3.1.2 Outgassing reduction

Before putting a material inside a vacuum system, its outgassing rate should be optimized for the specific application and required vacuum level. The following discussion is focused on the post-production treatments of special materials for the jaws of the collimators in the LHC vacuum system; when possible, similar consideration has to be taken into account also by the material supplier. The most common method to reduce materials outgassing is by heating: bake-out and vacuum firing are the two mostly used. Besides the thermal treatments, other surface techniques are employed to further decrease the outgassing.

3.1.2.1 Surface treatments

The chemisorption of gas molecules on the surface of the material is influenced by the surface roughness: higher surface area (*e.g.* higher roughness) provides more adsorption sites to the molecules. For this reason, especially for stainless steel, surface treatments such as electropolishing, diamond machining and mirror polishing by mechanical polishing techniques are used to reduce the roughness. It is proved that these treatments reduce the outgassing rate. [16]

The hydrocarbons, left by the production and post-production handling can be removed by a proper solvent or detergent cleaning, while the oxide or carbonized surface layer, which can trap gases, is removed by acid pickling.

Finally, it is proved that a coating of boron nitride (BN) or titanium nitrate (TiN) can act as a passive barrier that avoid gases to be released and consequently reduce the outgassing rate.

3.1.2.2 The bake-out procedure

If we remove the surface contaminants by a proper chemical cleaning, the outgassing flow coming from a material, which has been exposed to air, is dominated by water vapour ($\geq 80\%$) [13]. The water molecules, in fact, thanks to their strong polarity, can easily stick to the metal surface through electrostatic forces. Therefore, the reduction of water outgassing is paramount to reach the UHV condition.

In order to understand the way to reduce the water outgassing it is important to define some physical quantities:

- The mean stay time (sojourn time) τ_d , defined by the Frenkel's law, where τ_0 is assumed to be 10^{-13} s.

$$\tau_d = \tau_0 \cdot e^{\frac{E_d}{k_B \cdot T}}$$

Where:

- E_d is the binding energy [eV]
- k_B is the Boltzmann constant [eV·K⁻¹]
- T is the temperature [K]
- The fraction Θ of sites on the surface of the material already occupied by others gas particles.
- The total number of sites N_S

- The effective pumping speed⁵ S

At this point, we can write a balance equation for the variation of the quantity of gas, which is equal to the difference between the gas removed by the pump and the gas desorbed from the surface⁶ [12]:

$$\begin{cases} V \cdot \frac{dP}{dt} = -S \cdot P + \frac{N_S \cdot \Theta}{\tau_d} \\ \frac{d\Theta}{dt} = -\frac{\Theta}{\tau_d} \end{cases}$$

The solution is well approximated, for $t > \tau_d$, by:

$$P(t) \sim \frac{N_S}{S \cdot \tau_d} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_d}}$$

We can observe in Figure 20 that the time needed to reach a certain pressure is a function of the binding energy, which depends on the type of gas and material. For water molecules, the typical binding energy is 62-100 kJ/mole ($3.87 \cdot 10^{23}$ eV/mole).

⁵ It takes into account the effective pumping speed at the pump aperture and the gas flow restriction between the vacuum vessel and the pump that reduces the pumping speed.

⁶ These equations neglect the gas readsorption on the surface, but similar result is obtained considering it.

Figure 20: Pump-down time for different binding energy and temperature. If we consider the same binding energy, by heating the system we can reach the same pressure in a shorter time.

If we consider that, at $t=0$, some molecules are already in the gas phase, the curves slightly change (See Figure 21).

Figure 21: Pump-down time considering molecules already in gas phase at $t=0$.

Being the sojourn time an exponential function of the temperature, there is also a strong dependence of the pump-down from this variable: if we want to decrease the duration of the pump-down, it is important to raise the temperature.

Even if the water molecules are released from the surface of the material, they are rapidly reabsorbed as soon as the material is exposed to air with its humidity: it is thus necessary to perform an in-situ bake out to be sure that, once desorbed, the material cannot absorb water anymore. A component, to be compatible with the UHV environment of LHC, must be bakeable: the material properties should not change after the heating and the geometry of the component should allow the installation of proper heating collars or jackets. An example of a collimator with its heating jacket is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: A collimator ready for the vacuum test with the heating jacket for the bake-out.

Higher temperature and duration of the bake-out allow reaching lower outgassing value: a compromise between cost and benefit has to be found. In the Table 8, an example of the specific outgassing rate⁷ at room temperature after bake-out in function of the treatment temperature is given [12].

⁷ Outgassing rate per unit surface.

Table 8: Specific outgassing rate value of stainless steel at room temperature after different thermal treatment.

Unbaked stainless steel (10 h of pumping)	$3 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ mbar} \cdot \text{l} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$
Baked stainless steel (150 °C, 24 h)	$3 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ mbar} \cdot \text{l} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$
Baked stainless steel (200 °C, 24 h)	$2 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ mbar} \cdot \text{l} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$
Baked stainless steel (300 °C, 24 h)	$5 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ mbar} \cdot \text{l} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$

At CERN, the bake-out temperature for stainless steel is generally 250°C and the typical duration is 24h, except for the fully assembled collimators: for these components the maximum temperature is maintained for 48 h. The heating jacket is applied on the collimator vacuum tank; once it reaches the maximum temperature, almost 20 h are needed before observing a pressure peak. This delay is related to the time constant of the thermal system, which is dominated by radiation; hence to ensure a proper bake-out of the jaws a longer duration must be considered.

Some studies show that, after each bake out, collimators outgassing is reduced by a factor 1.3. [17]

3.1.2.3 The vacuum firing procedure

It is explained before that also the bulk of the material can be a source of outgassing. Metals can dissolve only a small amount of atoms that, at room temperature, are immobile in the lattice. Hydrogen⁸ is an exception: thanks to its small dimensions, it can travel and can be released also at room temperature. The distance that hydrogen travels in austenitic stainless steel in 1 day is covered in 1000 years from oxygen. For this reason, after bake-out, the metal outgassing

⁸ Coming from metals ores, tools needed for fusion, refractory materials of furnace, combustion and treatment gas, etc.

spectrum is dominated by hydrogen. In order to decrease the hydrogen content, a thermal treatment is performed. The temperature, in fact, increases the diffusion of hydrogen atoms, as it is shown in the Arrhenius equation:

$$D = D_0 \cdot e^{-\frac{E_b}{k_B \cdot T}}$$

Where:

- D_0 is the diffusion coefficient when temperature goes to infinity (same units of D)
- E_b is binding energy [eV]
- k_B is the Boltzmann constant [eV·K⁻¹]
- T is the temperature [K]

The atoms that reach at the surface can then recombine to form H₂. Moreover, differently from water, the hydrogen is not reabsorbed when the material is exposed to air: the treatment, which is called vacuum firing, can be done before the bake out and the sample can be exposed to air afterward. For a proper degassing of the bulk, the distance travelled by hydrogen molecules must be maximum: it is thus important to know that the diffusion length is function of both the temperature and the duration of the treatments:

$$L_{diff} = \sqrt{D(T_f) \cdot t_f}$$

Some typical values for stainless steel are visible in Figure 23: it should be noticed that, below 500° C, the diffusion is too slow; on the contrary we cannot increase arbitrarily the temperature and abnormal grain growth and recrystallization must be taken in consideration.

Figure 23: Diffusion length for stainless steel with different temperature and duration of the treatment

A numerical example of the vacuum firing effect on the H₂ outgassing is shown in the Figure 24.

Figure 24: Hydrogen outgassing of stainless steel before and after vacuum firing. At room temperature, the value for the fired one is lower than the apparatus sensitivity and is it extrapolated.

For porous material, like graphite, this treatment is also used to burn superficial contamination, instead performing a solvent cleaning that may be absorbed by the porosities.

If we consider thick sample (greater than 1.5 cm), the vacuum firing affects the hydrogen content of the external part and it is not influenced by the hydrogen pressure in the system. On the contrary, for small sample which are completely emptied, the hydrogen inside the material will be in equilibrium with the one in the furnace and it is thus influenced by its pressure in the furnace [18].

At CERN the recommended treatment for stainless steel vacuum firing consists of 2 h at 950 °C. Different vacuum furnaces (in figure 25 and 26) are present at CERN: their maximum temperature and dimension are different, but they are all equipped with a system of pumps able to keep a vacuum level of almost 10^{-5} mbar at 900 °C.

Figure 25: VAS furnace. Maximum temperature 1600°C, used for small samples.

Figure 26: Vacuum furnace at CERN, used for vacuum brazing of large components.

3.2 Vacuum acceptance tests criteria

Despite the fact that pressure requirements are different for each particle accelerator, general criteria are defined to establish vacuum acceptance limits of installed materials and equipment. In order to guarantee stable operation to the accelerator complex and in particular to the LHC, different tests are performed on the materials before the installation [17], including measurements of:

- Leak tightness
- Outgassing rate
- Gas analysis
- Virtual leaks

3.2.1 Leak tightness

In a vacuum system, there is an external leak when gas molecules penetrate the vacuum barrier increasing the system pressure: the leak can be described with

the number of air molecules entering the system per unit time. The unit of measurement is thus $\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. A leak can be provoked by a crack in a weld or by a faulty sealing. It is important to detect a leak, even if the pressure remains within the specified limits, as it is an indication of system defect and its deterioration with time cannot be predicted. If a big leak is present, it should be noticed from the slope of the pump-down curve: the expected ultimate pressure will be limited by the leak rate, as can be seen from Figure 27.

Figure 27: Typical pump-down curves in double-logarithmic scale for a metallic system (red), for a polymeric material (blue, $1/\sqrt{t}$ behaviour) and for a system with an external leak (green).

In case of very small leaks the only possibility to detect them is the use of a leak detector connected to the vacuum system or the use of a residual gas analyser⁹, tuned on helium mass (amu 4). The resulting helium leak rate must stay below $10^{-10} \text{ mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ for the acceptance of the component.

⁹ The Residual Gas Analyser (RGA) is a mass spectrometer; its working principle will be explained in the next chapter[16]

3.2.2 Outgassing rate

The maximum pressure is a parameter driven by beam requirements: from the beam lifetime, which depends on the beam gas scattering, and from the beam downtime, the allowed time to restart the machine in case of components exchange. Moreover, some elements, such as the RF cavities, require staying below a certain pressure to operate safely.

The outgassing rate Q is related to the pressure by the following formula:

$$P = P_0 + \frac{Q}{S}$$

where P_0 is the ultimate pressure that can be reached in the system.

All the accelerator system are designed with a proper pumping system and a fixed distributed pumping speed: therefore, the outgassing rate has to be adjusted to respect the beam lifetime. The following discussion will focus on the LHC and, in particular, on collimator in the LSS and transfer line¹⁰, since the resulting outgassing limits depend on the sector pumping speed and its requirements.

At the beginning of the pump-down, it is important to keep the outgassing below a certain value to allow a fast recovery of operations, mainly in the injector complex. For the collimator, the most important thing is to respect the vacuum acceptance limits after bake-out, during the beam circulation. After the bake out, the main requirement of the vacuum system is to guarantee 100 hours of beam lifetime in stable condition: the maximum pressure able to satisfy this need is $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$ mbar, so it will lead to a maximum collimator outgassing rate threshold of $1 \div 2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mbar-l/s, since in those points the pumping speed is around 20 l/s [18].

¹⁰ Two beam vacuum lines, with a total length of 5.6 km, bring the proton or ion beam from the SPS to the LHC rings.

The outgassing is calculated 48 h after the end of the bake-out, when the pressure is considered stable. The contribution to the outgassing rate of a collimator is given by the stainless steel vacuum tank and by the jaws with the absorber material. The tank outgassing is estimated $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ mbar·l·s⁻¹, therefore the remaining $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ mbar·l·s⁻¹ is available for the absorber. If a sample is tested, its specific outgassing is calculated and then multiplied by 3950 cm², which correspond to the total absorber area in a secondary collimator¹¹.

3.2.3 Gas analysis

Each gas has a specific effect on the beam, since the interaction probability is different (see Section 1.3). In particular, hydrocarbons have a negative influence on the beam stability [17]. It should be also noted that certain gases, such as carbon monoxide (CO, amu 28), carbon dioxide (CO₂, amu 44), and nitrogen (N₂, amu 28) can decrease the non-evaporable getters¹² (NEG) pumping speed, therefore they must be limited [18]. The outgassing and the final pressure are thus important, but also the composition of the gases must be analysed with an RGA and a specific limit must be applied for each gas. After the bake out, the outgassing should be dominated by hydrogen, hence, the limits are normalized with respect to its current. A summary of the limits is given in Table 9 and they are represented by red lines in Figure 28 and 29.

¹¹ A collimator is made of 2 jaws with 8 blocks and 2 tapering.

¹² See Appendix A

Table 9: Acceptance limits for different gases

Mass peaks interval [amu]	Maximum acceptable ratio to mass 2 [amu] peak
3÷20	10
28	10
21÷32 (except 28)	100
44	20
33÷45	500
Larger than 45	10000

In the collimators assembly, different and complex steps are involved: it can happen that some contamination is detected also after the bake-out, as it is in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Normalized gas analysis with respect to hydrogen of a contaminated collimator.

Conversely, in Figure 29 we can see a compliant gas analysis.

Figure 29: Normalized gas analysis with respect hydrogen. In this case, collimator after-bake out respects the acceptance limits.

3.2.4 Virtual leaks

A virtual leak, conversely to a real one, originates inside the system. During the production or the assembly of a component, some atmospheric air can be trapped and very slowly pumped away once the sample is under vacuum.

The detailed procedure for its calculation will be explained in the next chapter. Concerning the LHC acceptance limits, the internal leak outgassing rate must be below $5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mbar-l/s. This threshold is fixed to assure that just 1 meter of NEG-coated beam pipes is saturated in 150 days, since the gases present in the air, especially N_2 , contribute to the NEG saturation.

3.2.5 Induced outgassing

In all the accelerators, the beam induced outgassing is a consequence of different phenomena.

- *Thermal induced outgassing*: the collimators, due to their vicinity to the beam, are hit by the particles depositing energy inside them. As a consequence, their temperature increases more than the one of other equipment. Different measurements show that the outgassing q has an Arrhenius type dependence on temperature [18]:

$$q(T) \propto e^{-\frac{E_d}{R \cdot T}}$$

Where:

- E_d is the activation energy for hydrogen diffusion (12000 cal⁻¹ K⁻¹ for the stainless steel)
- R is the perfect gas constant (1.99 cal mol⁻¹)
- T is the temperature [K]

Therefore, it is important to minimize the temperature increase to guarantee the conservation of a very low pressure.

- *Photon and electron induced desorption*: in an accelerator, we always have a complex and mixed radiation field. Being the LHC a circular accelerator, synchrotron radiation¹³ must be taken into account. The γ ray can induce the photoemission of an electron from the vacuum

¹³ Electromagnetic radiation induced by curvilinear trajectory of a charged particle approaching the speed of the light.

chamber. The emitted electrons, accelerated by the beam current, may release gas molecules from the surface or also other secondary electron [23]. In particular, this latest phenomena can affect the accelerator performance leading to the fast formation of an electron cloud, which causes beam instabilities. These phenomena can be reduced with a proper thermal treatment (e.g. bake out, vacuum firing) and with a proper cleaning procedure, but the choice of the material has an essential role. In order to be compatible with the LHC UHV environment, a material must have a low secondary electron yield: the ratio between the incident and the emitted electron must be minimum.

CHAPTER 4

Experimental set-up

For a complete vacuum performance characterization of a new material, before the installation inside an accelerator, different instruments are used: their experimental set-up, function and characteristics will be explained in this chapter. Besides the characterization of the new composites, several techniques to improve their outgassing behaviour are tested; relevant features of these methods are shown below.

4.1 Outgassing measurements

4.1.1 Layout and instrumentation

One of the most important property to assess is the outgassing rate of a material, together with its gas composition. In order to foresee the quantity of gas which will be released in the accelerator, a vacuum test bench is used to reproduce conditions similar to the LHC environment. Its schematic is shown in the Figure 30.

Figure 30: Schematic of the outgassing test bench.

The test bench is made of two or more stainless steel vacuum chambers connected through flanges.

The pumping action is carried out by different pumps [26]:

- The primary pump (PP) is a displacement pump which accomplishes its function by mechanically trapping, compressing and releasing the gases. Oil is used as coolant, lubricant and seal: if the pump stops, a safety valve must avoid oil flow into the system. The minimum pressure that can be reached with this pump is around 10^{-3} mbar.
- The turbomolecular pump (TMP) is a momentum transfer pump which removes the gases thanks to fast moving blades that deviate the flux. It is effective when the gases are in the molecular regime¹⁴: thus, it is

¹⁴ The mean free path of the molecules is greater than the chamber dimension: the probability to hit the blades is thus greater than the collision between the particles.

used in series with a primary pump, and switched on at a pressure of 10^{-1} mbar. The lower limit varies as a function of its dimensions and can span from 10^{-7} to 10^{-10} mbar. Its action is not selective, but it gives a constant pumping speed for all gases.

- The sputter ion pump (VPI) is a capture pump [27]: the electrons, produced by an electrical voltage at the cathode (generally made of titanium), are helicoidally accelerated by a magnetic field. In this way, they have the possibility to ionize the gas molecules; the ions are then accelerated and implanted at the cathode. Moreover, their impact against the titanium can sputter it on the surface: thanks to its reactivity, the titanium can chemically bond the gases. The getterable gases (N_2 , CO, CO_2 and O_2) are reactive, thus they can be either chemically absorbed by the titanium or by implantation. For the noble gas (Ar, Ne, etc.) only the second mechanism is possible.
- The sublimation pump is an evaporable getter: a titanium filament is heated up by AC current and sublimates on the wall. The getterable gases can be bonded to titanium.

The pressure measurements are performed by different gauges:

- The dual gauge (PiBA): it is a full range gauge that combine a Pirani (Pi) and a Bayard-Alpert (BA). They both use an indirect measurements method, in the sense that they measure a pressure-dependent property of the gas. The principle of the Pirani is based on the fact that the heat conductance of a gas depends upon the number of molecules involved in the transport. A wire is electrically heated and the pressure is determined by measuring the current needed to keep it at constant temperature [28]. The linearity of this gauge is proved in the range $1 \div 10^{-4}$ Torr. When the pressure reaches the lower value, the dual gauge automatically switches to the other gauge. The BA is a hot

cathode ionization gauge: electrons are produced by a heated filament and accelerated by a voltage. Electron impacting against the gas molecules can ionize them; a collector attracts the positive ions and their current is measured. This current is proportional to the ion density and therefore to the pressure. Certain gases are easier to ionize, therefore the calibration of the BA is done with a specific gas, typically N_2 and correction factors are applied for the others. The lower pressure limit of this gauge is given by the X-ray, emitted at the anode by an impacted electron, which can induce photoelectron from the ion collector: their current cannot be distinguished from the positive ion current. If we consider a small size collector, like a wire on the axis of a grid anode, the minimum measurable pressure reaches 10^{-10} mbar [29].

- The two SVT are basically BA gauges, with a thin collector wire to reduce X-ray effect and with an extra electrode thanks to which the parasitic current can be estimated. The minimum measured pressure is around 10^{-12} mbar [29].
- The residual gas analyser (RGA) measures the partial pressures of the gases present in the system and it is thus important to understand the outgassing composition which, as it is explained before, must be taken into account to establish the conformity of a new material. Electrons, produced from a hot anode, ionize the gas molecules. The resulting ions pass through mass-to-charge ratio filter to be recognized by the ion detector which can be a Faraday cup or a secondary electron multiplier (SEM): the current measurements is proportional to the partial pressure. An excited ion can gain stability by a unimolecular reaction, called fragmentation, which leads to its decomposition in different species. Therefore, each gas is represented by different peaks

with a specific ratio between them. A summary of some common fragmentation patterns is given in Table 10 [16].

Table 10: Fragmentation patterns for common molecules

Molecule	Ion (M/z; Relative abundance %)
N ₂	N ₂ ⁺ (28;100), N ⁺ (14;13.7), ¹⁵ NN ⁺ (29;0.7),
CO	CO ⁺ (28;100), C ⁺ (12;8.8), O ⁺ (16;4.4), ¹³ CO ⁺ (29;1.1), CO ²⁺ (14;0.7)
O ₂	O ₂ ⁺ (32;100), O ₂ ⁺ (16;21.8)
Ar	Ar ⁺ (40;100), Ar ²⁺ (20;14.6), ³⁶ Ar ⁺ (36;0.3), ³⁸ Ar ⁺ (38;0.08)
CO ₂	CO ₂ ⁺ (44;100), CO ⁺ (28;6.7), O ⁺ (16;5.6), CO ₂ ²⁺ (22;1.4), ¹³ CO ₂ ⁺ (45;1.1), CO ¹⁸ O ⁺ (46;0.4)
H ₂ O	H ₂ O ⁺ (18;100), OH ⁺ (17;21.2), O ⁺ (16;0.9), H ₂ ¹⁸ O ⁺ (20;0.5)
CH ₄	CH ₄ ⁺ (16;100), CH ₃ ⁺ (15;88.7), CH ₂ ⁺ (14;20.4), CH ⁺ (13;10.6), C ⁺ (12;3.8), H ⁺ (2; 1.1)

The hole, indicated with the letter C in the test bench scheme (Figure 30), is a geometrical aperture in between the two vacuum chambers, with a diameter of 10 mm for the test bench involved in the following measurements. To calculate the outgassing rate, in fact, the pumping speed acting on the system is required. The pumping speed is known at the pump aperture, but it is difficult to estimate elsewhere. By inserting a restriction, we limit the pumping speed and this contribution is the dominant one with respect the pumping speed at the pump aperture which can be neglected. Therefore, the pumping speed S is simply given

by the conductance, which determine the volume of molecules per unit time that can cross the aperture:

$$S = \frac{1}{4} \cdot A \cdot \langle v \rangle = C' \cdot A$$

Where:

- A is the area of the aperture.
- $\langle v \rangle$ is the mean speed of a molecule, according to the kinetic theory of gas; therefore is proportional to $\sqrt{\frac{T[K]}{M[kg]}}$.

The conductance is, thus, different for all the gases; some value are shown in Table 11 for a reference temperature [30].

Table 11: Conductance for different gases.

Gas	C' at 293 K [$l \cdot s \cdot cm^{-2}$]
H ₂	44
He	31.1
CH ₄	15.5
H ₂ O	14.7
N ₂	11.75
Ar	9.85

Since the SVT gauges are calibrated with respect to N₂, the outgassing is calculated taking into account the nitrogen conductance. If we consider an aperture diameter of 10 mm and the N₂ conductance value, a pumping speed S of 9.22 l/s is found.

The outgassing rate can be calculated in this way:

$$Q = (P(SVT1) - P(SVT2)) \cdot S$$

The background outgassing Q_{bg} , measured in the same test bench without any sample inside, has to be subtracted, since all the instrumentation with hot filaments is a source of gas molecules (see Table 12).

Table 12: Outgassing value of the measurements tools in the system

SVT gauge [Torr·l/s]	$\sim 10^{-9}$
RGA [Torr·l/s]	$\sim 10^{-9}$

4.1.2 Procedure

When a sample is received in the vacuum facility, it is visually checked before its installation in the vacuum chamber to avoid contamination of the system by glue and surface oil. If it is necessary, a cleaning is requested. After that, the pump-down starts with the primary pump followed by the turbo-molecular one. When the pressure reaches the range of 10^{-6} mbar a leak detection is performed. After 24 h of pumping, the pressure is almost stable because the water vapour limits the minimum pressure that can be reached in the system. At this point, the RGA is switched on and the hot filaments suddenly start degassing; after 3 h the pressure is recovered and a mass scan can be performed. At this point, the bake-out cycle starts with a ramp of $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/h}^{15}$ up to a maximum temperature of $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This temperature is kept for 24 h and then the whole test bench is brought to $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, except for the SVT gauges which are at $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At this temperature, the SVT, the RGA, the VPI and the sublimator are degassed to remove further part of the contaminants. After that, the cool-down is carried out:

¹⁵ For the brazed collimator jaw, in which different material are in contact, a slower ramp is applied to avoid differential dilatation.

when the temperature is close to 100 °C and the pressure is about 10⁻⁹ mbar, the VPI is switched on and the TMP is isolated from the system to avoid water molecules to come back¹⁶. Once the whole test bench is at room temperature, after 48 h a scan is performed and the outgassing is calculated. If some traces of air (e.g. N₂, Ar) are found, the reason must be investigated. A leak detection is accomplished to exclude external leak, followed by an accumulation test. In order to evaluate the internal leak, the ion pump is switched off: the Ar is therefore no longer pumped, since it cannot react with the sputtered titanium of the sublimator. The nitrogen equivalent outgassing is calculated taking into account the pressure increase during the accumulation, its duration and the test bench volume:

$$Q_{N_2\text{equivalent}} = \frac{(p_2 - p_1) \cdot V}{t}$$

Where:

- p_1 is the initial pressure [mbar]
- p_2 is the final pressure [mbar]
- V is the volume in which the gas accumulates [l]
- t is the time without the ion pump [s]

Some gases are followed by the Multiple Ion Detection (MID) function of the RGA and, taking into account the maximum current of each gas, the percentage of Ar current (e.g. partial pressure) on the total one is calculated. In order to evaluate the Ar outgassing the nitrogen equivalent outgassing is multiply for the percentage of Ar. The Ar content in air is almost 1%, therefore if we multiply the Ar outgassing by 100 we can get an estimation of the internal air leak rate.

¹⁶ The Viton gasket in the pneumatic valve is a huge source of water outgassing.

In some cases, it is useful to repeat the RGA scan and the accumulation after different days at room temperature, to see if the outgassing is constant or decreases with time. When all the measurements are collected, the SVT, the RGA and the VPI are switched off and N₂ is injected in the chamber to restore the atmospheric pressure before opening it. The entire test requires at least one week.

4.2 Thermal desorption spectroscopy

The temperature is an important parameter when desorption is involved: the binding energy E_d of a gas can be overcome thanks to the thermal energy and the diffusion process can be activated. Therefore, heating a sample to induce the gas molecules degassing is an interesting method to investigate the bonding between a material and the gases. If an RGA is present in the system, the evolution of different species can be followed with the MID and the dominant mechanism can be determined. A thermal desorption spectroscopy apparatus (TDS) is able to heat a sample and detect the desorbed gas at every temperature. A scheme of the equipment used for this work is shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: Schematic of the TDS system.

The sample is positioned on a holder inside the pre-chamber; for this reason the sample dimensions must be carefully chosen: the section has to be a square of $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ and the thickness between $1 \div 3 \text{ mm}$. When a pressure of 10^{-7} mbar is reached inside, the valve is opened and the sample is positioned into the chamber. In this way, the measuring chamber is not exposed to air and a bake-out is not necessary every time. The chamber is equipped with a RGA to monitor the gases and the sample is heated by conduction through an electrical resistance (see Figure 32).

The maximum temperature is around $940 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the ramp can be between $10 \div 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to be sure that the sample follows the heating rate.

Figure 32: Sample heating in the chamber during a measurement. Courtesy of P. Massuti.

4.3 Secondary electron yield

The experimental set-up to evaluate the SEY of the materials consist of a metal and bakeable system, pumped with a turbomolecular pump and equipped with a BA gauge and a RGA. The sample is mounted on a rotatable holder. An electron gun sends the electrons toward the sample and then the current coming from the sample and from the secondary electrons collector is measured [31], as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Schematic of the SEY measurements apparatus.

The value is calculated as:

$$SEY = \frac{i_{SAMPLE}}{i_{SAMPLE} + i_{COLLECTOR}}$$

The measurement is repeated in three different points of the sample, to have some statistics, and after different electron conditioning times. It is proved, in fact, that if the sample is bombarded by electron, the SEY decreases. Therefore, its value is calculated for different electron doses, whose unit of measurement is Coulomb per millimetres square. The reason of this dependence is not completely clear, but it can be related to the decreasing of the oxide layer on the surface or to the stimulated emission of water molecules: it is proved that these features increase the SEY, and therefore their reduction can be beneficial.

4.4 Microscopic observation

As explained in the previous chapter, the porosities of the material can trap gas molecules. For this reason, once the composition of a material is known, is also important to understand and observe its microscopic configuration, which can

determine the outgassing performance of a material. The surface has an important role, but the voids can be also in the bulk of the material: the investigation technique must allow also a deeper investigation.

4.4.1 Scanning electron microscopy

To investigate in detail the surface of a material, the optical microscope is not sufficient, thus an electron microscope is preferred: the smaller wavelength of the electron allows to reach a greater enlargement. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) produces images by scanning the surface with electrons; they interact with the atom of the surface and produce different signal that can be detected. One of the most used is the signal coming from the secondary electrons, emitted by the excited atoms and detected by different tools. The electrons that can reach the surface without being lost come from the surface of the material; therefore to investigate the bulk of the material a particular sample preparation as to be applied.

4.4.1.1 Ion polishing

The sample is positioned on a holder and hit by an argon ion beam. With a minimum mechanical deformation, the surface grains, damaged by the machining, can be removed and the microstructure of the material becomes visible.

4.4.1.2 Focused ion beam milling

A possible alternative to observe the bulk of the material is the focused ion beam (FIB) milling. In this case the beam is made of gallium ions and a hole is created into the sample which is then observed through SEM. The FIB current is 1000 times lower than the current of ion guns used in the ion polishing, but its focusing capabilities is down to the nanometres scale, while for the ion gun is limited to millimetres.

4.5 Surface treatments

4.5.1 Carbon dioxide blasting

Liquid CO₂ is stored in a bottle and it is compressed to obtain its solid phase. Some pellets of solid carbon dioxide are sent onto the sample at high speed through a gun. The pellets sublime just after the impact with the material, absorbing heat from the surface almost immediately. This thermal shock provokes a stress wave that, combined with the kinetic energy of the CO₂ particle, can remove both the contaminant and the graphite flakes which are not well adhered to the surface. For this reason, the CO₂ blasting is considered a cleaning method, but it is also proved that by increasing the roughness of the surface it enhances the adhesion of metallic coating, if needed to increase the electrical conductivity of the material.

4.5.2 Ultra sound cleaning

Another common cleaning technique is based on ultra sounds. Sound waves propagate in a liquid (water, solvent, detergent) creating bubbles by the cavitation effect. These bubbles are empty spaces, thus very unstable: they implode producing stress waves on the surface of the material that can remove either the contaminant or carbon flakes not well attached in the case of graphitic materials. The power and frequency of the waves can be controlled and in particular the radius of the bubbles is determined by the frequency (see Figure 34).

Also, this treatment increases the roughness of the material and is thus a possible candidate for the surface preparation before the coating.

Figure 34: Bubbles radius dependency from the US waves frequency.

4.5.3 Diamond paste polishing

Conversely from the two previous treatments, this one is going in the opposite direction: diamond pastes of different particle size are applied on a rotating disk and the sample to polish is placed on it (see Figure 35). The material is progressively removed from the surface which results flatter and flatter: this goes in the opposite direction with respect the previous treatments which aim in removing the damage while increasing the roughness.

Figure 35: One of the polishing machine at CERN.

CHAPTER 5

Experimental results analysis

In this chapter, the results of the vacuum performance characterization of MoGr and CuCD are presented. The aims of this analysis are:

- Understand their compatibility with the LHC vacuum environment
- Find possible thermal or surface treatments to improve their behaviour
- Find possible weak points in the production process

5.1 Molybdenum carbide-graphite

The discussion concerning this material is divided into two parts: the first one is focused on the characterization of the material as received from the supplier; the second will illustrate the effects of the post-production treatments.

5.1.1 As received material

A MG6403Fc block, shown in Figure 36 and shaped as a real collimator absorber block, is firstly analysed.

Figure 36: A block of MG6403Fc of 125x45x25 mm, shaped as the collimator absorber blocks.

The pump-down curve in Figure 37 is very close to the experimentally found behaviour of a metallic material ($\propto t^{-1}$). This trend is observed for all the MoGr samples tested.

Figure 37: Pump-down curve of a block of MG6403Fc.

After the bake-out, the outgassing rate is above the LHC acceptance limits for the collimator absorbers¹⁷, as shown in Table 13, where:

- $Q - Q_{bg}$ is the outcoming of the outgassing test, calculated as explained in 4.1.1;
- Q_s is the specific outgassing, calculated dividing $Q - Q_{bg}$ by the area of the sample;

¹⁷ $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ mbar·l/s

- Q_{jaws} is the total contribution of the absorber material in a collimator and it calculated by multiplying the specific outgassing for 3950 cm^2 (see 3.2.2)

Table 13: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc.

Sample	$Q-Q_{\text{bg}}$ [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Q_{s} [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$]	Q_{jaws} [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]
MG6403Fc	$3.7\cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.9\cdot 10^{-10}$	$7.5\cdot 10^{-7}$

Analysing the graph in Figure 38, there is no high mass contamination ($\text{amu}>50$), but it is clear that the outgassing is not dominated by H_2 ($\text{amu } 2$) as envisaged in UHV components, but by air (N_2 , $\text{amu } 28$ and Ar , $\text{amu } 40$). A huge presence of CH_4 ($\text{amu } 15$ and 16) is detected.

Figure 38: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc.

The presence of air is almost always observed in graphite: the porosities of the material can be easily filled by gases either during the production process, if it is not performed under vacuum, or after successive exposure to air. In order to carry out the comparison, the graphite¹⁸ used for the collimators in the transfer lines is considered.

First, as it can be seen in Table 14, the total outgassing is more than one order of magnitude lower than MoGr and the limits of LHC acceptance.

Table 14: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of some blocks of graphite.

Sample	Q-Q _{bg} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q _s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q _{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
Graphite	6.7·10 ⁻⁸	1.3·10 ⁻¹¹	5.1·10 ⁻⁸

Looking at the gas analysis in Figure 39, the air content is recognized, but with respect to MoGr, the ratio amu 28 to 40 is 10 times lower: the argon content in the air is much lower, therefore the source of argon must be different. It is, in fact, confirmed that during the production process a high-temperature step is performed under argon atmosphere. The huge difference in the outgassing rate, together with the much higher peaks of mass 28 in MoGr, leads to the conclusion that in MoGr the air content is much higher.

¹⁸ Produced by SLG, grade R7550P5D.

Figure 39: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of some blocks of graphite.

If the TDS analysis of the two materials is observed, the argon content is almost negligible with respect to the other species (Figure 40 and 41). The MoGr TDS sample is also exposed to air for one month, but still, no air is detected (Figure 42). This is a clear indication of how the air is bounded: when a gas is chemically bounded to a material (chemisorption or physisorption), the bonding between a gas and a material is defined by the binding energy E_d . When this energy is provided through an increase of temperature (thermal energy), the gas starts being released. For this reason, in the TDS, different peaks correspond to different E_d and, from the activation temperature onward, the outgassing is often exponential with the temperature. On the contrary, the air molecules are just geometrically trapped into the porosities of material: the temperature gives them kinetical energy; therefore the mobility of the particle has a smooth dependence on the temperature (*e.g.* proportional to the square root of the temperature). There are no peaks corresponding to this kind of bonding and argon is thus difficult to

observe since, as soon as the temperature increases, the degassing of the other species becomes dominant. Some useful information can, however, be obtained by the TDS. We can notice in MoGr the presence of some high mass hydrocarbons (amu 41 and 43 in Figure 40) which can be related to mineral oil generally used in the primary vacuum pumps: the material supplier confirmed that a wrong operation of the safety valves can lead to some pump oil in the system used for the last treatment. A thermal treatment above 400°C is necessary to remove these pollutants. Moreover, the complete removal of water takes place at about 300°C: the standard bake-out temperature should be increased of 50°C.

Figure 40: TDS analysis of a sample of MG6403Fc as received.

Figure 41: TDS analysis of a sample of graphite as received.

Figure 42: TDS analysis of a sample of MG6403Fc as received and after air exposure.

In the light of these results, the difference between the graphite and the MoGr outgassing does not appear to be related to the chemical composition, but it must be researched in the structure of the material, which is deeply related to the production process. Graphite powders are generally mixed with a binder (containing coal or petroleum); when it is heated up, all the components of the binder, except carbon, evaporate. Such gas formation carries out a pressure on the material, which leads to the formation of porosities. On the contrary, the porosities in MoGr can be related to a wrongly oriented graphite flake, which leads to a lack of compaction. The porosities dimensions of graphite are therefore bigger than the one of MoGr, as can be seen from the SEM images of the TDS samples (from Figure 43 to 46) after ion polishing.

Figure 43: SEM image of MoGr after ion polishing.

Figure 44: SEM image of graphite after ion polishing.

Figure 45: Porosities typical dimensions of MoGr.

Figure 46: Porosities typical dimensions of graphite.

On the other hand, also on the surface layer (the first 5-10 μm) of the tested MoGr block, lot of cracks and porosities (see Figure 47 and 48) are observed: they can be related to machining and can be a source of air trapping as well.

Figure 47: SEM image of the block of MG6403Fc after FIB milling.

Figure 48: A zoom of the first damaged layers of the block of MG6403Fc after FIB milling.

The aim of this discussion is to understand if air trapped in MoGr is mainly related to the surface or to the bulk of the material: in the first case, a post production treatment can be applied, otherwise a modification of the production process must be considered.

The first step in this last direction has been done with the new plate: the MG6403He (2.1.1). The block in Figure 49 is vacuum tested as received.

Figure 49: A block of MG6403He of 125x36x15 mm, shaped as the collimator absorber blocks.

The outgassing rate of the block is even higher than MG6403Fc, as shown in Table 15.

Table 15: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403He.

Sample	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
MG6403He	$9.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$6.5 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Despite the fact that the CH₄ contamination disappeared, the air content is even higher (see Figure 50).

Figure 50: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG6403He.

The ratio between the ion current of mass 28 and 40 is almost constant, as it is shown in Table 16.

Table 16: Nitrogen to argon ratio for the two grades of MoGr.

Sample	I_{28}/I_{40}
MG6403Fc	46.9
MG6403He	62.3

The argon venting at the end of the sintering and post-sintering process has no impact on their final content; possible reason is that the durations of these

treatments are too short to degas the air from the plate and therefore, when the argon is injected, it cannot be absorbed by the material.

If we look at the SEM image of this block in Figure 51, a lots of porosities can be observed: the damaged area involved is almost of 10 μm , so deeper with respect to the MG6403Fc plate.

Figure 51: SEM image of the block of MG6403He after FIB milling.

Moreover, the green compaction under vacuum seems to be ineffective; it appears that the bulk of the material is not influencing the outgassing behaviour. However, since very difficult to reach a good level of vacuum during the green compaction, an improvement of this step may lead to a better result.

Since the new grade does not show the desired improvement, the production and therefore the following tests are performed on samples of the old grade (MG6403Fc). In order to have a better understanding of the outgassing and to check the reproducibility of the production process, samples coming from different plates are tested. In particular, an analysis of the effect of a different specimen thickness is performed. A thin sample, in fact, may not replicate the microstructure of a big sample. In this context, samples of two different thickness and section are tested; they are shown in Figure 52 and 53.

Figure 52: Bars of MG6403Fc of dimensions 10x12x120 mm.

Figure 53: A sample of MG6403Fc of dimensions 25x6x70 mm.

The results of the two tests are compared with the MG6403Fc block previously mentioned. As shown in Table 17, the specific outgassing of the bars is of the same order of magnitude of the block, while the one of the thinnest sample one order of magnitude lower: this result would lead to a total collimator outgassing compliant with the LHC acceptance limits.

Table 17: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of different samples of MG6403Fc.

Sample dimensions [mm]	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
45x25x125	$3.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$
10x12x120	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-6}$
25x6x70	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$7.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$

The difference between the bars 10 mm thick and the sample 6 mm thick is also evident in the gas analysis: the 10 mm (see Figure 54) has a behaviour similar to the block, dominated by air, while for the 6 mm sample the hydrogen contribution is the major one (see Figure 55¹⁹).

¹⁹ The RGA reaches its sensitivity limit, therefore the resulting background is very high.

Figure 54: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of bars of MG6403Fc 10 mm thick.

Figure 55: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a sample of MG6403Fc 6 mm thick.

In order to understand the reason of the better behaviour of the thin sample is important to point out all the differences between this sample and the block:

- the machining;
- the plate from which they are cut;
- the thickness;
- the orientation of the bigger surface.

This last point requires more focusing: a sketch of the cutting process is shown in Figure 56. It is evident that the bigger surface of the sample is parallel to the pressing direction, while for the block it is perpendicular. It is important to underline this aspect because the material shows a very anisotropic behaviour, which is related to the configuration of the graphite planes; it cannot be excluded that also the outgassing is influenced by this property.

Figure 56: Representation of the sample cut from the block.

A different machining may lead to a different surface state, which can play an important role in the vacuum performance. For this reason, the surface of the compliant sample is observed through SEM after FIB milling. The image in Figure 57 is similar to the block: the first 5 μm near the surface are characterized by porosities, probably related to the damaged induced by the machining.

Figure 57: SEM image of the 6 mm thick sample of MG6403Fc after FIB milling.

The surface damage is quite similar: not sufficient to justify such a difference in the outgassing behaviour. Therefore, other possibilities are taken into account. The samples come from different plates: an uncontrolled change of one production cycle parameter may lead to such a difference. The compliant sample comes from a plate called C2, so from now on we will refer to it as ‘C2’. First, the density of the C2 sample is slightly lower ($2.50 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) with respect the standard value found for MoGr ($2.55 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$). The initial idea is that the porosities dimension in the C2 are bigger and therefore it is easier to remove air from it; a more detailed analysis is performed to verify this hypothesis. The statistics is increased by acquiring more SEM images of the same sample. This goal is achieved thanks to FIB tomography: a section is milled and its image saved, then a further milling is performed to get the section behind. The operation is repeated more than 100 times in order to obtain a volume of almost $100\times 60\times 60 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. A 3D reconstruction is then performed and a Matlab script is used to distinguish

carbides, carbon and voids. The analysis is performed in two locations of two samples: one coming from the plate C2 and one coming from a plate with higher density ($2.76 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$). Their 3D reconstruction is shown in Figure 58 and 59.

Figure 58: Carbide region in the higher density sample (C8).

Figure 59: Carbide region in the lower density sample (C2).

The volume fraction estimated from the images are summarized in Table 18.

Table 18: Volume fraction of each component and estimated density for the two sample for MG6403Fc.

Sample	Position	Density [$\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$]	Volume fraction graphite [%]	Volume fraction carbide [%]	Volume fraction void [%]
C2	C2_1	2.36	89.3	3.8	6.9
	C2_2	2.55	91.2	5.5	3.4
	Average	2.45	90.3	4.5	5.1
C8	C8_1	2.68	85.6	8.4	6.1
	C8_2	2.64	87.4	7.4	5.2
	Average	2.66	86.3	7.8	5.7

The density estimated taking into account the volume fraction and the carbide/graphite density (in Table 19) is very similar to the measured one. Then, the void fraction in the two samples is almost similar (5.1% against 5.7%), while the difference in the carbide content is higher. Therefore, the C2 sample may have a lower density, not because of a large void fraction, but because a lower content of carbide, whose density is higher.

Table 19: Carbide and graphite density used to estimate the density of each sample.

Material	Density ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$)
Molybdenum carbide	8.9
Graphite	2.3

This lower carbide fraction can be related to a higher liquid carbide loss during the sintering: a higher temperature can induce this effect and also a changing in the graphite structure that lead to a better outgassing performance.

Nevertheless, we should remind that this sample has the lowest thickness and the orientation of its bigger surface is different from the other samples. The bake-out performed during the vacuum test may be enough to degas air from the sample. For this reason, a block of 6 mm with the same orientation of the C2 sample is cut from a block in which air is found. The outgassing values in Table 20 is anyway out of the acceptance limits and the gas analysis in Figure 60 still shows the dominant contribution of air. Therefore, if we start from a sample which contains air, we cannot degas it by decreasing its thickness. The sample C2 of 6 mm has a complaint behaviour because it comes from a plate with different characteristics with respect the others.

Table 20: Outgassing rate values of a 6 mm thick sample from a non-compliant block.

Sample dimensions [mm]	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
15x6x70	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Figure 60: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a 6 mm sample from a non-compliant block.

5.1.2 Effects of the thermal and surface treatments

5.1.2.1 *The vacuum firing*

Since the block and the bars of MG6403Fc and the block of MG6403He show a similar behaviour if tested as received, different treatments are applied on different samples and just the relative improvement is taken under consideration.

First, a vacuum firing of 2 h at 950°C is performed on the block of MG6403Fc. As can be seen in Table 21, the outgassing rate is decreased by a factor lower than 3.

Table 21: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc before and after a vacuum firing of 2 h at 950°C.

Treatment	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
None	$3.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$
2 h firing	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$7.1 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Looking at the graph in Figure 61, it is clear that this improvement is mainly related to the decrease of the CH₄ content. The graph is not normalized for the H₂ ion current so that we can observe that H₂ is almost constant, conversely to what observed for stainless steel.

Figure 61: RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc before and after vacuum firing of 2 h at 950° C.

After this treatment, the material is still not compliant with the LHC acceptance limits, both in term of outgassing rate and gas analysis. For this reason, it was decided to increase the duration of the treatment to 48 h; this longer vacuum firing is found to be very effective for the graphite of the transfer lines collimator, as can be seen in Table 22: the outgassing is reduced more than a factor 10.

Table 22: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of some blocks of graphite before and after a vacuum firing of 48 h at 950°C.

Treatment	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
None	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
48 h firing	$4.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$9.1 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$

From Figure 62, the decrease of the air content (N₂, O₂, Ar) is evident.

Figure 62: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of some blocks of graphite before and after vacuum firing of 48 h at 950°C.

In terms of outgassing rate, the effect of the longer vacuum firing on the MoGr is very similar to what observed on graphite. The result of this test, performed on the 8 bars of MG6403Fc shown before, is reported in Table 23 and the outgassing is reduced by almost one order of magnitude.

Table 23: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of bars 10 mm thick of MG6403Fc before and after a vacuum firing of 48 h at 950°C.

Treatment	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
None	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-6}$
48 h firing	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Nevertheless, the gas analysis, shown in Figure 63, indicates that the N₂ is partially removed, while Ar is slightly increased. If we compare the mean velocity of Ar and N₂, the second one is faster thanks to its lower mass. Therefore, the resulting conductance and outgassing will be higher. The N₂ degassing during the thermal treatment can be more effective, leading to a lower content in the gas analysis. A longer duration or a higher temperature of the treatment may be useful also for Ar. As shown in the SEM images, graphite has bigger porosities, therefore the thermal degassing through vacuum firing may be more effective.

Figure 63: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of bars of MG6403Fc before and after vacuum firing of 48 h at 950° C.

5.1.2.2 The carbon dioxide blasting

The MG6403Fc block, after firing, is treated with the CO₂ blasting on all the surfaces. The aim of the test is to evaluate if the treatment can detach some grains from the surface of the block and eliminate the first 10 μm of damaged material.

However, the Table 24 shows that the treatment increases the outgassing of a factor 50.

Table 24: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc before and after CO₂ blasting.

Treatment	Q-Q _{bg} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q _s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q _{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
Before CO ₂ blasting	1.4·10 ⁻⁸	7.1·10 ⁻¹¹	2.8·10 ⁻⁷
After CO ₂ blasting	7.1·10 ⁻⁷	3.6·10 ⁻⁹	1.4·10 ⁻⁵

Looking at the gas analysis in Figure 64, the air content is increased and there is evidence of CO₂ adsorption: these effects lead to a higher outgassing rate.

Figure 64: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out a block of MG6403Fc before and after CO₂ blasting.

The CO₂ adsorption is confirmed also by the TDS test: in Figure 65 a comparison is shown between the CO₂ outgassing of a sample as received and after the treatment. The blasting increases the CO₂ content, especially the first one, which is related to the surface outgassing. The energy (e.g. the temperature) required to degas a molecule from the surface, in fact, is lower than the one necessary to bring it to the surface and then to degas it.

Figure 65: TDS analysis of mass 44 of a sample of MG6403Fc as received and after CO₂

The SEM images in Figure 66 shows that the surface damage is still present and therefore it can be the air trapping source. The shock induced by the surface treatment could have also increased the damage.

Figure 66: SEM image of CO₂ blasted sample after FIB milling.

Despite the deterioration of the performance, this test is important because the CO₂ is a superficial treatment: the fact that by changing the surface state we change the outgassing performance is an indication that the surface plays an important role. As confirmed by the SEM, the surface is still damaged. This result indicates that in case of coating of MoGr, a different surface preparation has to be done to avoid an increase of the outgassing rate.

5.1.2.3 The ultra sound (US) cleaning

The US cleaning is considered a possible candidate to prepare the surface before a coating: by removing contaminants and increasing the surface roughness, it enhances the coating adherence. The idea is that the stress induced by the explosion of cavitation bubbles may remove the surface damage observed in MoGr. The US cleaning is performed on the block of MG6403He and after that a

vacuum firing of 48 h is performed. The thermal treatment is necessary to evaporate all the solvent that may be absorbed during the cleaning to avoid the contamination of the test bench. The outgassing, as shown in Table 25, is one order of magnitude lower. The same improvement is found in MoGr just after a 48 h vacuum firing, the US cleaning effect seems to be negligible.

Table 25: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403He before and after US cleaning and 48 h vacuum firing.

Treatment	Q-Q _{bg} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q _s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q _{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
None	9.0·10 ⁻⁸	6.5·10 ⁻¹⁰	2.6·10 ⁻⁶
US cleaning + 48 h firing	6.6·10 ⁻⁹	4·10 ⁻¹¹	1.6·10 ⁻⁷

Also, the gas analysis in Figure 67 shows the same effect found for the sample only vacuum fired: the N₂ is reduced while the Ar is almost constant. In the gas analysis, the Ar peak seems higher than before, but this is related to the fact that H₂ peak is lower and the scan is normalized to its current.

The SEM image (Figure 68) confirms that the surface damage is not removed; therefore it is still not clear if the source of the air content is just the surface or also the bulk of the material.

Figure 67: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG6403He before and after US cleaning.

Figure 68: SEM image of CO₂ blasted sample after FIB milling.

5.1.2.4 Diamond paste polishing

Since the US cleaning is not effective in the removal of the damage, diamond paste polishing with particle size of 2 μm and then 1 μm is performed on the block of MG6403He. During the polishing, lots of carbon particles are produced and the sample is then cleaned with water and ethanol. For this reason, before the vacuum test the sample is fired. The outgassing value in Table 26 are still out of the limits and the gas analysis in Figure 69 shows that air is still the dominant gas.

Table 26: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403He before and after diamond paste polishing.

Treatment	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Q_s [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$]	Q_{jaws} [$\text{mbar}\cdot\text{l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]
Diamond paste	$1.9\cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.4\cdot 10^{-10}$	$5.4\cdot 10^{-7}$

Figure 69: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG6403He before and after diamond paste polishing.

The SEM images are taken also after this treatment, but this time the damage seems to be disappearing: the surface appear very flat and regular (Figure 70).

Figure 70: SEM image of diamond paste polished block after FIB milling.

The bottle neck of the air source must, therefore, be researched elsewhere; despite the surface damage playing an important role, air is still present even when the surface state improves.

5.1.2.5 The coating

The previous tests show that the removal of air from the material is very difficult. For this reason, a coating of pure Mo of 8 μm is applied on all the surfaces of the block of MG6403Fc, to see if a barrier can prevent the air to be outgassed. A layer of Mo is chosen because, thanks to its good electrical conductivity, it is one of the possible candidates to coat graphite or MoGr, in order to minimize the collimator contribution to impedance. The coating is

realized through Mo ion sputtering. The outgassing results shown in Table 27 goes in the opposite direction: the outgassing is very high.

Table 27: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc after Mo coating.

Treatment	Q-Q _{bg} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q _s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q _{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
Mo coating	5.3·10 ⁻⁷	2.7·10 ⁻⁹	1·10 ⁻⁵

Gas analysis in Figure 71 confirms the dominating role of air.

Figure 71: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG6403Fc with Mo coating on all the surfaces.

5.1.2.6 The new compaction process

A block of MoGr from a second material supplier, with a different production process, is received at CERN and vacuum tested. The sintering and post-sintering

process are quite similar to the previous one in term of duration and temperature. The main differences concern the first step of the production: the compaction. The powder are, in fact, compressed in two steps: during the first one, a uniaxial compaction a 5 MPa is performed. Then, the plate is put in a vacuum bag and isostatically compressed in water at 300 MPa. A block shaped with the new collimator absorber design is then machined (see Figure 72).

Figure 72: MoGr block from a new supplier. For convention, it is named Nd7401Sr.

A vacuum firing of 48 h at 950°C is performed before the outgassing test, whose results are reported in Table 28: for both the material supplier the results refer to the test done after the same thermal treatment. As can be seen, the new material has an outgassing rate more than one order of magnitude lower and therefore compliant with the LHC acceptance limits.

Table 28: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of two fired blocks of MoGr from two suppliers.

Sample	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
Supplier #1	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Supplier #2	$4 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-8}$

The gas analysis in Figure 73 show that the dominant gas is H₂, as it should be after bake out. The spectra is all compliant except the peak or Ar: the Ar is not used during the production process, but it was the gas used to recover atmospheric pressure after the vacuum firing.

Figure 73: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of Nd7401Sr after vacuum firing.

In order to verify if the Ar is coming from the vacuum firing, the same treatment is performed but this time, Ne is used to vent. After this treatment the outgassing rate is decreased of a factor 4 (see Table 29) and, the peak of Ar is partially replaced by the one of Ne (amu 20), as can be seen in Figure 74. This means that the thermal treatment remove part of the gas from the material and therefore the empty space is fill with the venting gas. After this treatment, the peak of air is just slightly above the acceptance limits.

Table 29: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of MoGr block after first and second firing.

Treatment	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
Ar venting	$4 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Ne venting	$9.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$6.3 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$

Figure 74: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of MG xx after vacuum firing with Ar or Ne venting.

An accumulation test is also performed to assess the internal leak compatibility of the material. As can be seen in Figure 75, when the ion pump is switched off, the Ne and the Ar start increasing.

Figure 75: Gas accumulation of Nd7401Sr block after Ne venting.

The internal leak rate is evaluating taking into account both the Ne and the Ar outgassing, since it is supposed that Ne could be replaced by air if a the vacuum firing venting is done with air. The outgassing of Ar and Ne in Table 30 is summed up and then the value is extrapolated for all the MoGr present in a collimator. The internal leak value is found to be $2.3 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ mbar} \cdot \text{l} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ which is therefore compliant with the LHC acceptance limits for the internal leak ($5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ mbar} \cdot \text{l} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$).

Table 30: Calculation of the internal leak rate.

deltaP [mbar]	Time [s]	Volume [l]	QN2equiv [mbar·l/s]	QNe [mbar·l/s]	QAr [mbar·l/s]	QAir [mbar·l/s]
$2.7 \cdot 10^{-9}$	7200	13	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$8.3 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$8.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$

5.1.3 Secondary electron yield

Three samples of MG6403Fc are measured as received and after different conditioning time (e.g. different electron dose). The results are very similar for the three samples, therefore just one is shown. As it can be seen in Figure 76, a maximum value lower than 1.2²⁰ is reached at an electron energy of about 250 eV, for the as-received sample. The initial conditioning increases the value up to a maximum value lower than 1.3, but then, going on with the electron bombardment, the SEY decreases as expected. The maximum value found is lower than in case of stainless steel (around 2): the metallic carbide are not playing an important role and the material is compliant with the LHC limits.

Figure 76: SEY measurements of MG6403Fc as received with different conditioning time.

²⁰ For its calculation see 4.3

If exposed to air, the oxide layer, which increases the SEY and it is removed by conditioning, can be replaced by a new one: for this reason, the measurements are repeated after 1 week of air exposure. As shown in Figure 77, the SEY is higher than the value found after the longest conditioning, but still lower than the as received sample.

Figure 77: SEY measurements of MG6403Fc after 1 week of air exposure.

The results are compared with what obtained for graphite of the collimators in the transfer lines. As it can be seen in Figure 78, the behaviour is very similar to the MoGr: the maximum value for the as received sample is lower than 1.2, it slightly increases after the first conditionings and, after that, it decreases. The SEY seems to be governed mainly by the atomic number of the materials, which is very similar for graphite and MoGr, due to the small fraction of metal in MoGr.

Figure 78: SEY measurements of graphite as received with different conditioning time.

5.2 Copper diamond

The first sample of CuCD tested is a block produced in 2015 with Cu cladding (see Figure 79); due to a non-proper handling of the material during years, a cleaning was needed prior putting it in a vacuum environment. A US cleaning is therefore performed before the outgassing measurements.

Figure 79: A block of CuCD shaped as a real collimator absorber with a copper cladding.

The sample is put in the test bench and the pump-down starts from the atmospheric pressure. As can be seen in Figure 80 (orange curve), the pressure after 20 h of pump-down is higher than 10^{-3} mbar, therefore too high to start the bake out in the test bench. For this reason, a thermal treatment at 250°C is performed for 48 h in one of the vacuum furnace. After that, the pump-down is much faster (blue curve); therefore, even if the slope is still different from the one of a metallic surface, the bake out was started.

Figure 80: Pump-down curve of CuCD block before and after 48 h bake-out.

As it can be seen in Table 31 and in Figure 81, the outgassing and the gas analysis are compliant with the LHC acceptance limits: the first one is below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ mbar \cdot l \cdot s $^{-1}$ and the RGA scan is dominated by H_2 .

Table 31: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a block of CuCD.

Sample	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
CuCD block	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$7.4 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-8}$

Figure 81: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a block of CuCD.

The difficulties in the first pump-down may come from the cleaning: since it is done in water, the material could have absorbed part of it. The US cleaning must, therefore, be avoided for this material or a longer bake-out must be performed before the test or the installation in the collimator. Nevertheless, it cannot be excluded that the long exposure to air has caused the high outgassing before the bake-out: this has to be verified because it can be a problem during the technical stop of the accelerator since the collimators are exposed to air.

A second sample (in Figure 82), coming from a different supplier and without a copper cladding, is then tested.

Figure 82: CuCD sample without copper cladding.

During the pump-down (see Figure 83) no problems are detected and the slope follows the t^{-1} trend.

Figure 83: Pump-down curve of CuCD sample without Cu cladding.

After bake-out, the outgassing (see Table 32) and the gas analysis (see Figure 84) are compliant with the LHC limits.

Table 32: Outgassing rate values after bake-out of a sample of CuCD.

Sample	$Q-Q_{bg}$ [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]	Q_s [mbar·l·s ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²]	Q_{jaws} [mbar·l·s ⁻¹]
CuCD sample	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$7.4 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-8}$

Figure 84: Normalized RGA Scan after bake-out of a sample of CuCD.

The two tests indicate that the CuCD has a good compatibility with the UHV environment; anyway, the reason for the initial pump-down problems must be analysed to understand if thermal treatment before the installation can solve the

problem or if each time the sample is exposed to air a longer pump-down time has to be taken into account.

CHAPTER 6

Conclusions

In every particle accelerator, an Ultra High Vacuum (UHV) environment is necessary to guarantee beam stability and lifetime. In case of high-energy accelerator, a collimation system is mandatory to intercept the particles deviating from the ideal trajectory: the amount of energy stored in the beam would induce quenches in the superconductive magnets. In the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), at CERN, more than 100 collimators are installed; on top of having excellent thermo-mechanical properties, they must be compliant with the UHV acceptance limits. A collimator is made of two jaws enclosed in a vacuum tank. The most important jaw element is the absorber: due to its vicinity to the beam, it is required to be a good electrical conductor to minimize the RF impedance, which induces instabilities in the beam. In view of the High Luminosity upgrade of the LHC, new families of low-impedance collimator absorber are studied. The aim of this work is to investigate the vacuum compatibility of Molybdenum Carbide-Graphite (MoGr) and Copper Diamond (CuCD), two of the most promising materials for the upgrade of the collimation system.

In order to give a complete overview of the behaviour of these materials, different set-ups were adopted. An outgassing test bench was used to evaluate the total amount of gas released: the thermal desorption spectroscopy (TDS) was exploited to understand the species contained in a material. Other techniques included different microscopic methods to investigate the microstructure and the surface state, and a dedicated test bench to evaluate the secondary electron yield (SEY) of the material.

The analysis of the TDS of MoGr suggests that the ideal bake-out temperature should be at least 300°C to completely remove water; moreover, a thermal treatment above 400°C has to be performed to get rid of the high-mass hydrocarbons accumulated during the production process. The measurements performed in the outgassing test bench showed that the main problems with MoGr are the non-compliant outgassing rate and the significant presence of air, which must be limited in the LHC to avoid Non Evaporable Getter (NEG) saturation. Air is always observed in graphitic materials, but the quantity detected in MoGr is often much higher. The microscopic analysis of the two materials reveals that the porosity dimensions in graphite are much bigger than in MoGr, as also confirmed by the density comparison. The amount of gas that can enter in graphite porosities is therefore higher; however, the size of the pore-connecting channels is also bigger. For this reason, the outgassing mechanism in graphite is much faster with respect to MoGr and the outgassing rate measured after 48h is lower. This mechanism is controlled by the bulk structure. Nevertheless, surface effects are also observed: in MoGr samples a damaged surface with a thickness between 5 µm and 10 µm is always observed. These cracks and porosities are related to the machining and they can be a source of air trapping as well. Only one of the samples was found within the acceptance criteria: this result could be related to the higher temperature reached during the sintering process. However, at such temperature, the repeatability of the process is not easy to achieve. In order to improve the performance, a new grade of MoGr (MG6403He) was produced with the compaction step performed under vacuum, to decrease the air trapped in the porosities since the beginning, but no improvement was observed. Moreover, despite the fact that argon instead of air was used to vent the chamber after the sintering and post sintering, its relative percentage in gas analysis with respect to nitrogen was not different: the duration of the treatments may not be long enough to degas air from the material. As a consequence, the material cannot even absorb the argon.

After a first characterization of MoGr as received from the supplier, a series of thermal and surface treatments were performed to verify if a post-production treatment could decrease the outgassing rate. One of the important conclusions is that the duration of the vacuum firing must be at least 48 h at 950°C. The decrease in outgassing after this treatment is much higher with respect to the one induced by a 2 h firing at the same temperature. As mentioned before, the surface state can play an important role in the outgassing behaviour. To act on this parameter, two surface treatments were investigated: the CO₂ blasting and the US cleaning. Such treatments are also adopted to prepare the material surface in view of a thin-film deposition, necessary for some family of collimators. CO₂ blasting was found to increase the outgassing rate by almost two orders of magnitude. This treatment should thus be avoided, but it was useful to confirm the importance of the surface of the material in the outgassing performance. The US cleaning effect seems instead to be negligible. Nevertheless, a lot of parameters are involved in this cleaning (US power, the solvent used, the duration of the treatment); before its application on big series productions, a more detailed study of its effects has to be performed. An additional test to probe the surface effect on outgassing was performed after polishing one of the samples with a diamond paste. The microscopic analysis of the surface seems to indicate a complete removal of the surface damage, but the outgassing was still out of the limit and the air content was still dominant. Despite the fact that the surface plays an important role, the material is still not compliant even when the surface damage is removed. Therefore, the main air content is likely trapped in the bulk of the material. All the surface and thermal treatments performed on MoGr were not successful to reduce the material outgassing rate below the LHC acceptance limits. Nevertheless, the material from a second supplier has a compliant outgassing, with a much lower content of air. This improvement can be related to the fact that air is removed before sintering or to the fact that the lower compaction pressure leads to bigger porosities, from which it is easier to remove the air. Overall, it seems that a lower

material compaction is beneficial for vacuum compatibility, as mentioned in the graphite case. A production of a new plate with a lower compaction pressure from the first material supplier has been forecast to confirm this hypothesis. An increase of the duration of the post-sintering treatment at high temperature can also be a possibility to try to remove part of the air.

The secondary electron yield of MoGr is compliant with the specification for the LHC and no surface treatment to improve it is required. Its performance is comparable to that of graphite.

From what concerns Copper-Diamond (CuCD), the first tests performed indicate that the outgassing behaviour and gas analysis of the material are compliant with the LHC requirements. One of the blocks was cleaned with US and, after that, the pump-down before bake-out, in the UHV test bench, was not successful. New samples must be exposed to air to check that this problem was not related to the prolonged exposure, but just to the cleaning procedure applied before the UHV test. In the future, measurements should also be performed to verify the SEY behaviour of the material and the compatibility with the collimator specifications.

APPENDIX A

Non Evaporable Getters

A surface can provide a pumping action if it is able to absorb and retain molecules for the needed duration. The so-called getters can satisfy this requirement, thanks to a chemical reaction that leads to a strong bonding between the getter surface and the gas molecules. In order to efficiently bond the particles, the surface has to be clean and there are two ways of producing a clean getter surface: by in situ deposition of a getter film or by heating an oxidized getter to let the oxygen on the surface diffuse into the bulk. In the second case, we speak about non evaporable getters (NEG) and the temperature to obtain oxygen diffusion is called *activation temperature*. The NEG in the LHC is applied as a coating of a TiZrV alloy on the stainless steel beam pipe; hence, if the activation temperature is compatible with the bake out temperature, the getter may be activated during the thermal treatment without the necessity of electric feed-throughs and powering control. The pumping principle of the NEG is based on the formation of a chemical bonding: hence, they cannot pump inert gases such as argon or methane [21].

On the NEG surface, different adsorption sites may accommodate one molecule without being desorbed. Moreover, hydrogen can also diffuse within the NEG bulk at room temperature. When all the adsorption sites are occupied, the NEG is saturated. All the gases pumped contribute to the saturation of the surface: CO, CO₂, H₂O, N₂, and O₂. [22]. Nitrogen, in particular, can occupy six to eight adsorption sites. It is thus important to keep under control the quantities of these gases in the LHC beam pipes since NEG contribution is essential to reach the desired low-pressure value and assure the designed beam lifetime to the operation.

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